

TREASoURcE

D5.4 Value chain models, mapping, and procedures

WP no and title	WP5 KVC-DEMOS: Circular biobased side and waste streams for biogas and fertilizers
Lead Beneficiary	MTK
Responsible Author	Nora Berglund
Contributors	Jaana Koivisto, Magdalena Edvardsen, Tran Ngo, Jan Bakke, Torbjørn Kristiansen, Charlotte Forsberg, Eva Liisa Vahtramaa, Teele Joost, Marion Kade, Jaanus Tamm, Jelizaveta Krenjova-Cepilova, Margit Kull, Xuewei Liu, Gerardo A. Perez-Valdes

This document contains the "D5.4 Value chain models, mapping, and procedures" for the TREASoURcE project (Grant Agreement No. 101059491).

Project Details			
Project acronym	TREASoURcE	Start / Duration	June 2022 / 48 months
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRCBIO-01-01 – Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)'s circular systemic solutions	Grant Agreement No	101059491
Type of Action	Innovation Action (IA)	Coordinator	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd
Contact person	Ugur Kaya, ugur.kaya@vtt.fi		
Website	https://treasource.eu/		

Deliverable Details			
Deliverable No	5.1		
Deliverable Name	Value chain models, mapping, and procedures		
Work Package	5		
Dissemination level	PU	Type	Report
Due Date (M)	34	Submission date	25.3.2025
Lead Beneficiary	MTK - The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners	Responsible Author	Nora Berglund

Deliverable Contributors				
	Name	Organisation	Role / Title	E-mail
Deliverable leader	Nora Berglund	MTK	Project Manager	nora.berglund@mtk.fi
Contributing Authors	Jaana Koivisto	EKOF	Project Manager	jaana.koivisto1@tampere.fi
	Magdalena Edvardsen	Frstad	Project Manager	magedv@fredrikstad.kommune.no
	Tran Ngo	VTT	Research Scientist	tran.ngo@vtt.fi
	Jan Bakke	Østfold	Project Manager	janbakke@ofk.no
	Torbjørn Kristiansen	Østfold	Project advisor	torbjornkr@ofk.no
	Charlotte Forsberg	Østfold	Project Manager	charlotf@ofk.no

	Eva Liisa Vahtramaa	TLN	Expert in Organized Waste Management	evaliisa.vahtramaa@tallinnlv.ee
	Teele Joost	TLN	Project Manager	teele.joost@tallinnlv.ee
	Marion Kade	TARTU	Project Assistant	marion.kade@tartu.ee
	Jaanus Tamm	TARTU	Project Manager	jaanus.tamm@tartu.ee
	Jelizaveta Krenjova-Cepilova	TalTech	Project Manager & Researcher	jelizaveta.krenjova@taltech.ee
	Margit Kull	TalTech	Researcher	margit.kull@taltech.ee
	Xuewei Liu	SDU	Postdoctoral Researcher	xuli@igt.sdu.dk
	Gerardo A. Perez-Valdes	SINTEF AS	Research Scientist	gerardo.perez-valdes@sintef.no
Reviewers	Jaana Koivisto	EKOF	Project Manager	jaana.koivisto1@tampere.fi
	Magdalena Edvardsen	Frstad	Project Manager	magedv@fredrikstad.kommune.no
	Tran Ngo	VTT	Research Scientist	tran.ngo@vtt.fi
Final review and quality approval	Ugur Kaya	VTT	Project Coordinator	ugur.kaya@vtt.fi

Document History			
Date	Version	Name	Changes
30.1.2025	1	D5.4_v1	First draft
14.2.2025	2	D5.4_v2	Second draft based on first review round
3.3.2025	3	D5.4_v3	Third draft based on second review round distributed to Management Committee
21.3.2025	4	D5.4 Value chain models, mapping, and procedures	Reviewed final version

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS.....	7
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	8
INTRODUCTION.....	9
2. TERRITORIAL VALUE CHAIN CREATION.....	11
2.1. Mapping of the ecosystem.....	11
2.1.1. Value chain creation.....	16
2.2. Mapping in the project countries.....	18
2.2.1. Mapping in Denmark – Material flow analysis.....	18
2.2.2. Mapping in Finland.....	20
2.2.3. Mapping in Norway.....	22
2.2.4. Mapping in Estonia.....	26
2.3. Stakeholder mapping.....	28
2.3.1. Bio refineries and industries utilizing biobased side and waste streams....	29
2.4. Cooperative models.....	31
2.4.1. Cooperative and limited company.....	32
2.4.2. Producer organization.....	32
2.4.3. Collaboration with municipalities.....	33
2.5 Østfold’s mobile solution.....	33
2.5.1. Findings from preliminary mapping and market inquiries.....	34
2.5.2. Findings and assessments from inquiries with selected providers.....	34
2.5.3 Concluding assessments.....	34
2.6 Fredrikstad’s new post-sorting and treatment plants’ value chains and logistics..	35
2.6.1. Challenges in scaling up of production.....	35
2.6.2. Opportunities for optimization and scale-up.....	36
2.7. Challenges identified and most potential streams for future use.....	37
2.7.1. New innovations to promote use of biobased side streams.....	39
3 CREATING MARKETS AND E-MARKET FOR ORGANIC SIDE STREAMS.....	41
3.1 Launch and progress after the launch.....	42
3.1.1. Technological development.....	43
3.1.2. Marketing of the digital marketplace.....	46
3.1.3 Future of the marketplace.....	50
3.2 Replication of marketplace in Estonia.....	51
3.2.1 The Qualitative Study: Evaluating the Transferability Potential in Estonia..	52
3.3 Replication of marketplace in Norway.....	58
3.4 Public procurement promoting the use of biobased resources.....	58
3.4.1. Municipalities’ interests towards biogas and recycled fertilizers.....	59
3.4.2. Case examples of municipalities promoting biogas.....	60
4. BIOGAS INCENTIVES – POLICY BRIEF.....	62

4.1. Policy brief: The continuation of biogas incentives must be ensured..... 63

5. REFERENCES 65

ANNEX 1 – BIOBASED SIDE AND WASTE STREAMS 69

ANNEX 2 – KIERTOASUOMESTA.FI MARKETING MATERIALS 71

ANNEX 3 – POLICY BRIEF FOR BIOGAS INCENTIVES 73

ANNEX 4 – ØSTFOLD – FLOWCHART FOR POTENTIAL UTILIZATION OF STRAW 77

List of Figures

Figure 1. Ecosystem of biobased side and waste streams (adapted from original by Karen Marie Aanonsen / Østfold)..... 12

Figure 2. The valorisation technologies presented in Tran Ngo’s thesis (2023), (Adapted from Lohri et al., 2017)..... 15

Figure 3. The value chain of biobased side and waste streams from perspective of biogas and recycled fertilizers. 16

Figure 4. Example of a local bioeconomy model based on agricultural streams. 17

Figure 5. Energy potential from animal manure, Østfold. 24

Figure 6. Buffer zone around farming fields. Fredrikstad Municipality 25

Figure 7. Stakeholder mapping for the value chain models of bio-based side and waste streams... 29

Figure 8. Visualization of ØAS operation. 35

Figure 9. The stakeholders connected through KiertoaSuomesta.fi platform. 41

Figure 10. The content page articles include information mainly about circular economy and agriculture..... 44

Figure 11. CE Christmas calendars 2023 (left) and 2024 were published on the marketplace’s social media accounts. 48

Figure 12. Written article in Siipikarja (Poultry) - expert magazine. 48

Figure 13. Video about biobased side streams published in February 2025. 49

Figure 14. Value proposition. Methodology for the survey and interviews. 53

Figure 15. Customer profile. Methodology for the survey and interviews. 54

List of Tables

Table 1. Amount of manure in pilot municipalities, tonnes. 21

Table 2. Energy potential from selected agricultural and forestry bio-based waste, Østfold 23

Table 3. Stakeholders identified in the stakeholder mapping for bio KVC with WP2. 28

Table 4. Key industries utilizing biobased side and waste streams. 30

Table 5. Key events, in which KiertoaSuomesta.fi has been presented. 46

Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
AD	Anaerobic digestion
API	Application programming interface
AR	Arealressurs (Norwegian for land resource)
BAU	Business as usual
CE	Circular economy
D	Deliverable report
EKOF	Ekokumppanit Oy (EcoFellows Limited)
FME	Safe feature manipulation engine
Frstad	Fredrikstad kommune
GIS	Geographic information system
KVC	Key value chain
MTK	The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners
NIBIO	Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research
ØAS	Norwegian Østfold Avfallssortering IKS
Østfold	County of Østfold
SDU	Syddansk Universitet
SR	Skogressurs (Norwegian for forest resource)
TalTech	Tallinna Tehnikaülikool
TARTU	Tartu Linn (Tartu City)
TLN	Tallinna Linn (City of Tallinn)
TWh	Terawatt hours
VTT	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

This deliverable, D5.4 Value chain models, mapping, and procedures, is part of work package 5, which focuses on circular biobased side and waste streams and on promoting the use of these resources, for example, for biogas and recycled fertilizer production. The report provides a comprehensive overview of creating and developing value chains for biobased side streams, presenting innovative solutions and collaboration models among various stakeholders.

The report begins with an introduction that outlines the significance of biobased side streams in the circular economy. It then delves into the creation of territorial value chains, mapping ecosystems that include agricultural, forestry, and urban side streams and stakeholder mapping. Examples of these biobased side streams include manure, grass, straw, and municipal sludge. Biomass mappings conducted in the project are also described. The report also discusses the development of the KiertoaSuomesta.fi digital marketplace, which connects producers and users of biobased side streams. Additionally, it addresses challenges related to the use of biobased side and waste streams and provides policy recommendations for promoting biogas production and recycled fertilizers.

The key findings of the report highlight the importance of efficient use of biobased side and waste streams to tackle issues related to climate change, reduce dependence on fossil fuels, and enhance supply security. The report emphasizes the need for collaboration between various stakeholders, including farmers, municipalities, and industries, to create and develop value chains for biobased side streams. It presents innovative solutions and cooperative models to promote the use of biobased side streams, such as biogas cooperatives and collaboration with municipalities.

Overall, the report offers valuable insights into the potential of biobased side streams in the Circular Economy and provides recommendations for policy and practice to support their efficient use and market development.

INTRODUCTION

The TREASoURcE project aims to promote the circulation of under-utilized side streams. One of the three key value chains focused on is biobased side and waste streams. Work package (WP) 5 concentrates on identifying added-value use and new business models for these resources and promoting market development for them. Biobased side and waste streams refer to materials of organic origin that are generated during production but are not part of the main products. These streams can come from various sectors, such as agriculture, forestry, and the food industry - for example, from farms, forest estates, or food processing facilities. While the production of biogas and recycled fertilizers have been a major focus, other higher-value opportunities for recovering these streams have also been explored.

Nutrient recycling maximizes the use of organic materials, such as manure, grass, plant residues, processed biowaste, by applying them as fertilizers to the soil. This process closes nutrient loops, reduces waste, and promotes sustainable resource management. Rich in organic matter, these recycled materials enhance soil structure and fertility, support plant health, and decrease reliance on synthetic fertilizers. By utilizing these resources, farms and industries can improve self-sufficiency and reduce dependence on costly, finite mineral fertilizers. Additionally, biogas production converts organic materials into renewable energy, such as heat, electricity, or transportation fuel, and produces digestate, a nutrient-rich material for fertiliser use. Together, these solutions enhance supply security, lower environmental impact, and reduce reliance on fossil fuels, delivering both economic and ecological benefits.

Efficient use of the biobased side and waste streams is important, to tackle issues related to climate change and reducing reliance on fossil fuels and other finite resources. It also helps to improve waste management and to reduce waste. Through efficient use of these biobased resources, the need for imported fertilizers (nutrients) and energy could be decreased with significant environmental benefits. In the current geopolitically uncertain world, particularly in Europe due to the ongoing war of aggression in Ukraine, the importance of supply security and self-sufficiency has become increasingly evident. Biobased side and waste streams can play a significant role in enhancing these aspects.

Large volumes of biobased side and waste streams are generated in the EU annually. Despite their potential, only a limited fraction is utilized efficiently. The amount of biowaste generated in agriculture and industry sectors has increased from 2012 to 2022 in the EU, and during the same time the recovery of the biowaste from these sources has decreased (European Commission, 2024). However, comprehensive data on the utilization of side streams is largely lacking, making it difficult to assess their full potential. This data gap has posed a significant challenge for projects like biomass mapping, where the absence of reliable statistics often forces reliance on rough estimations rather than precise assessments.

The objectives of WP5 on biobased side and waste streams align with the EU's targets to promote a circular bioeconomy. The European Green Deal aims to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. This

strategy supports the TREASoURcE project's objectives by encouraging the efficient use of biobased side and waste streams, reducing reliance on fossil fuels, and enhancing supply security. Initiatives, such as the new Circular Economy Action Plan (European Commission, 2020) and the Farm to Fork Strategy (European Commission, 2020b), further emphasize the importance of sustainable resource use and market development for these streams. Regulatory frameworks also play a key role in promoting the utilization of biobased side and waste streams. For example, the Waste Framework Directive mandates the separate collection of biowaste to facilitate its recovery, supporting the efficient use of organic resources and their integration into circular value chains (EC Directive 98, 2008).

Several reports have already been published by the TREASoURcE project team which have included valuable information about biobased side and waste streams. These reports have been published on the resource.eu - project website (TREASoURcE, 2025).

The reports include:

- [D1.1 Territories' CE activities and state-of-the-art of CE](#) presenting an analytical framework of biobased side and waste streams (TREASoURcE, 2023).
- [D1.3 Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains](#) providing an overview of the regulatory framework for the value chain (TREASoURcE, 2024).
- [D1.4 State-of-the-art analysis of technologies, circular business models and ecodesign practices for plastic waste, end-of-life electric vehicle batteries and bio-based side and waste streams](#) presenting technologies used to produce biogas and circular fertilizers, (TREASoURcE, 2023b).
- [D5.1 Digital marketplace](#) describing the work to prepare for the launch of the marketplace, (TREASoURcE, 2023c).
- [The operational environment of circular bio-based side and waste streams for biogas and nutrient recovery](#), Master's thesis (Ngo, 2023).

2. TERRITORIAL VALUE CHAIN CREATION

The creation of territorial value chains is a complex process that requires a comprehensive understanding of the ecosystem in which biobased side and waste streams operate. This chapter examines the key components of value chain development, focusing on ecosystem mapping, stakeholder engagement, and resource valorisation. By identifying the interconnections between agricultural, forestry, and urban biobased streams, the project aims to foster more efficient resource use and enhance circular economy principles.

The following subchapters provide a structured approach to this process. First, subchapter 2.1 explores ecosystem mapping as a fundamental step in understanding the landscape of biobased side and waste streams. This involves identifying key material flows, processing opportunities, and regulatory conditions that shape the operational environment. Subchapter 2.2, then, delves into the country-specific mapping efforts undertaken in Denmark, Finland, Norway, and Estonia. Together, these sections lay the groundwork for a targeted and systematic approach to territorial value chain creation, ensuring that biobased resources are effectively integrated into circular systems.

2.1. Mapping of the ecosystem

The agricultural, forestry, and urban side and waste streams examined in the project cover a wide range of materials. Together with their associated value chains, they create an interconnected ecosystem of biobased side and waste streams. These biobased streams are valuable resources that can be directly used for fertilization or soil improvement but also have significant potential for further processing in industrial applications. They can be utilized and transformed into biogas, recycled fertilizers, soil amendments, bedding materials, and biochar, among other products.

The simplified Figure 1. 'Ecosystem of biobased side and waste streams' visualizes the ecosystem, highlighting key flows such as agricultural side streams and food waste, which, along with municipal sludge, are processed into energy and fertilizer use, in this case at a biogas plant. The outputs - biogas for electricity, heating, and transportation, as well as digestate as fertilizer - demonstrate the potential for closing nutrient loops and creating renewable energy.

While the focus is on agriculture, the Figure 1 does not account for other vital sectors, such as the food industry and forestry, which were also considered in the broader context of the project work. These sectors play crucial roles in enhancing nutrient recycling, reducing emissions, and creating value-added applications for biobased resources, ultimately contributing to a circular and sustainable bioeconomy.

Figure 1. Ecosystem of biobased side and waste streams (adapted from original by Karen Marie Aanonsen / Østfold).

In Finland, Norway, and Estonia, which were the primary focus of WP5, side and waste streams produced were listed to excel sheets to create a comprehensive overview of available resources. These lists were then combined into a single document, which can be found in Annex 1. Further details on country-level mapping are presented in chapter 2.2, "Mapping in the project countries".

Examples of the biobased side and waste streams:

- Livestock manure
- Grass biomass
- Straw
- Contaminated / excess feed
- Wetland vegetation
- Residues from horticulture
- Logging residues; stumps, wood chips
- Solid biowaste
- Municipal sludge

In agriculture, the largest biobased side streams in terms of volume are manure, grass and straw. Biobased side streams are valuable raw materials for direct use such as fertilizers or soil improvers and are also increasingly demanded by the processing industry. For example, the gradual reduction of peat production in the EU will increase the need for alternative organic bedding materials. Unlike grass and straw, which can be left on the fields to benefit soil quality, manure is subject to specific regulations regarding its storage and application. For instance, manure spreading has seasonal restrictions to prevent nutrient runoff. During these periods, farmers must ensure proper storage facilities

and carefully time and plan the spreading of manure to comply with the regulations. The recycling of nutrients and materials contributes to circular economy (CE) and reduces the use of virgin raw materials. Efficient use of materials improves the environmental sustainability of production through energy and resource efficiency. Biogas and recycled fertilizers are good examples of more efficient resource use and are described below.

Biogas

Biogas is a renewable energy source produced through the anaerobic digestion of organic materials, such as biobased side streams and waste. This process transforms waste materials into valuable biogas and digestate, which can be used as renewable energy and nutrient-rich fertilizer, respectively. Biogas production supports circular economy goals by turning waste into resources, helping reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and decreasing dependence on fossil fuels and fertilizers produced with fossil energy.

Biogas production offers numerous environmental and economic advantages. It enhances energy security and self-sufficiency, reduces the need for synthetic fertilizers through recycled nutrients, and supports local economies. By reducing emissions, biogas also contributes to climate goals, such as carbon neutrality. Furthermore, the increasing use of biogas in transportation, particularly as liquefied biogas for heavy vehicles, is an example of the growing role of biogas in the energy transition. Biogas can be produced from a range of biobased side and waste streams. Utilizing these residues not only supports sustainable waste management, nutrient recycling and energy generation, but also enhances rural development.

Recycled Fertilizers

Recycled fertilizers are nutrient-rich products derived from biobased side and waste streams. These fertilizers are designed to recover essential nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus and return them back to the soil, supporting sustainable agriculture and reducing dependency on synthetic fertilizers. Using recycled fertilizers improves soil fertility and structure by introducing organic matter. This boosts microbial biodiversity, enhances water retention, and reduces nutrient leaching. Recycled fertilizers also contribute to circular economy goals by repurposing waste into valuable agricultural inputs, minimizing nutrient losses, and promoting resource efficiency.

Recycled fertilizers are versatile and suitable for various crops and farming systems. A wide range of products with different nitrogen-to-phosphorus ratios is already available, and new options continue to emerge as processing and refinement technologies advance, offering farmers increasingly tailored nutrient solutions. By replacing synthetic fertilizers, recycled fertilizers not only reduce environmental impacts but also help farmers lower input costs while maintaining crop yields. Incorporating recycled fertilizers supports sustainable farming practices and addresses global challenges such as nutrient imbalances and resource depletion. Their use plays an important role in supporting rural economies and contributing to broader climate and environmental goals.

The mapping of the ecosystem for biobased side and waste streams has been carried out through several measures, including questionnaires, interviews, workshops and a literature review. A master's thesis has also been published describing the framework: "The operational environment of circular bio-based side and waste streams for biogas and nutrient recovery" (Ngo, 2023). It presents comprehensive overview of the circular biobased side and waste streams' operation, valorisation methods used for the resources, regulations affecting the ecosystem and digital solutions available. In addition to a literature review conducted, the thesis involves three case studies which represent circular bioeconomy operational models of self-sustaining circularity, rural-urban symbiosis, and industrial ecosystem. 10 expert interviews and 1 questionnaire targeted to primary producers were conducted to gain insights for the case studies. The state-of-the-art analysis of technologies used to produce biogas and circular nutrients presented in the master's thesis were also published in a report D1.4 (TREASoURcE, 2023b).

Ngo's thesis (2023) identifies that key elements impacting the operation of the ecosystem are feedstock availability and quality, technical operation, financial viability, policy and legislation change, social acceptance, resource competition, and virgin material alternatives. Ngo discusses that commonly adopted technologies, such as composting and anaerobic digestion, face challenges in ensuring product quality, which stem from feedstock issues and unsustainable material design; advancements addressing these root causes could improve efficiency and cost-effectiveness. The potential of digital tools is also investigated in the thesis, including digital marketplaces, and AI, in facilitating circular bioeconomy transitions, though these require substantial infrastructure and high-tech adaptation. While policies promoting the ecosystem, such as biowaste separation mandates and renewable energy targets, are progressing, challenges like unharmonized regulations, limited incentives, and inadequate financial support for small operators are pointed out. (Ngo, 2023)

The primary producers' questionnaire in Ngo's thesis explored biobased side and waste stream production, treatment practices, and associated challenges from the primary producers' perspective. As a result, manure was identified as the primary type of biobased side and waste streams, with over 35% of respondents reporting annual production exceeding 100 tons. Crop residues followed, with around 30% of respondents indicating similar production levels. (Ngo, 2023)

The most common treatment and recovery practices found in the thesis for the biobased streams include direct use (land application and animal feed) and paying for waste management services. Other notable practices are fertilizer recovery and trading of the streams. However, 8% of respondents reported leaving the biobased side streams untreated. Key challenges in current handling practices include a lack of guidance for disposal (especially for agricultural plastics, which often end up in mixed waste), logistical issues in remote areas, high management costs, difficulties in achieving economic viability for recovery practices, and challenges in discovering markets for the resources.

Inhibiting factors for onsite treatment of self-sustaining biobased side and waste stream practices and trading possibilities found in Ngo's thesis include insufficient quantities of the streams, lack of investment, and limited time and human resources. One respondent noted that utilization can require more

resources than the benefits it provides. Regarding trading of the materials, challenges include insufficient quantities for sale and low demand from buyers. Despite these obstacles, 15% of respondents considered trading as a potential solution.

Ngo's thesis (2023) concludes that the systemic transition to the circular bio-based side and waste streams ecosystem is driven by the collaboration of diverse stakeholders, integrating technological push, market pull, political support, and sociocultural shifts that encourage the widespread adoption of circular products and services. A well-functioning circular ecosystem requires close interlinkage between small-scale self-sustaining models, medium-scale rural-urban symbiosis, and large-scale industrial ecosystems. Especially, fostering small-scale, self-sufficient circularity is crucial. Indeed, this strategy enhances nutrient recovery, minimizes transportation needs, and mitigates related environmental impacts. When self-sufficiency is not viable, a medium-scale rural-urban symbiosis can be established to tackle logistical challenges, maximize the use of bio-based and waste materials, and refine feedstocks for industrial applications. Ultimately, large-scale industrial ecosystems are needed to recirculate industrial byproducts and utilize feedstocks processed through rural-urban symbiosis, bridging the gap in feedstock quantity and quality between small primary producers and industrial operators. (Ngo, 2023)

Figure 2. The valorisation technologies presented in Tran Ngo's thesis (2023), (Adapted from Lohri et al., 2017)

2.1.1. Value chain creation

Early in the project, it became evident that agricultural side and waste streams hold the greatest potential for more efficient utilization. While all biobased side streams from agriculture, forestry, and the food sector were considered, the focus was directed toward agricultural biomass to enhance project outcomes. This scope refinement enabled more targeted work and better results. Less attention was paid to forestry side streams, as it was found that they are already exploited due to a well-organised forestry industry, for example through energy wood, which has a relatively high market value and utilisation rate. Additionally, food industry side streams are primarily managed through waste management solutions, which, in comparison to agriculture, were generally seen as more effectively addressed.

An illustration of the value chain of biobased side and waste streams focusing on biogas and nutrient recovery was developed (Figure 3). It highlights the interconnected stages of circular resource use, starting from bio-production: agriculture, forestry, and green areas, which generate primary products and side streams. These streams are processed through different methods, such as anaerobic digestion and composting, yielding outputs such as recycled fertilizers, soil amendments, and biochar, as well as biogas for energy. Logistics and storage are important links between each part of the value chain. The value chain illustrates all stakeholders within the system but does not reflect that most side streams generated in agriculture, particularly, are directly utilized on farms. These streams often bypass the broader network of actors in the chain. National and EU frameworks, including regulations, strategies, and funding, play a central role in supporting and guiding the system, ensuring the functioning of the value chain.

Figure 3. The value chain of biobased side and waste streams from perspective of biogas and recycled fertilizers.

Similar figures to Figure 3 were created for the relevant stakeholders associated with the value chain. Stakeholder identification was an important part of the value chain formulation discussed in chapter 2.3. Stakeholder mapping.

Stakeholders were engaged in the value chain creation. Two workshops were organized; first on 17.1.2023 in Tampere “Utilizing biobased side streams more efficiently” which was also organized to gain insights for the digital marketplace, at the time of the development phase. Another workshop was held in Tampere on 30.10.2023 which aimed to identify challenges and bottlenecks of the biobased side and waste stream ecosystem. This event also served to validate the value chain model produced.

In addition to the workshops, two questionnaires about side and waste stream production and use were sent to primary producers, and separately to the industry sector, in both Finland and Estonia. However, these questionnaires resulted in few responses, leading to the decision not to conduct them in Norway, as originally planned. Consequently, the ecosystem mapping was carried out through discussions with the internal and external experts of the project team.

To explore the potential for biogas production, particular attention has been paid to improving the utilisation of agricultural side streams. Task 5.4 “Powering local economies through circular bioeconomy” has focused on the feasibility of farmers investing in a shared biogas plant. This approach allows for shared ownership and operational responsibility, making the initial investment easier to implement and sharing the associated risks between several stakeholders. By assessing the viability of such a co-operative model, the project aims to identify ways in which farmers can benefit from biogas production in terms of both additional income and resource efficiency. The shared biogas plant concept offers a promising opportunity for farmers to actively participate in a circular bioeconomy, increasing local sustainability while improving economic outcomes.

Figure 4. Example of a local bioeconomy model based on agricultural streams.

The Figure 4 illustrates such a local bioeconomy model, which is centred on a biogas plant based on agricultural side streams. It is built and operated by a limited company owned by local farms. The joint ownership reduces the investment costs for individual farms and spreads the associated risks compared to an individual farm-level biogas plant. The joint biogas plant can provide additional income through energy sales and affordable recycled fertilizer for farm use. Collaboration can enable more efficient utilization of resources and decrease costs for logistics, improving the plant's profitability. The figure has been created as part of the T5.4.

In this example, the farms invest in the plant and are responsible for its operations. Additional farms, even if not part of the limited company, can contribute biomass to the biogas plant. The biogas plant produces digestate, which can be sold as fertilizer also to the 'external' farms with fertilization needs, further supporting circular nutrient recycling. The energy generated by the biogas plant is utilized in two ways: it can be supplied for local needs or sold to the gas grid, creating a diversified revenue stream for the limited company. This model demonstrates how local collaboration among farms and the establishment of a shared enterprise can promote decentralized energy production, enhance nutrient recycling, and generate economic benefits for the participating stakeholders.

2.2. Mapping in the project countries

The lack of accurate national-level data on biobased side and waste streams was a major challenge in creating a comprehensive overview of available biomasses. Due to this reason a comprehensive mapping of all biobased side and waste streams in the project countries Estonia, Finland and Norway was not conducted. Due to the same reason, despite efforts to focus on these countries in the T1.2 'National and regional value chains, logistics and material flow mappings', a decision was made to focus on Denmark, where more data was available.

The biobased side and waste streams from Estonia, Finland and Norway were primarily mapped in qualitative manner. Initially, all side streams available in the project countries were listed to separate excel sheets and later modified and combined into one document, found in Annex 1. While all three project countries also aimed to collect quantitative data of the side streams on national level, limited data availability led to a shift in approach. Instead, the most promising resources were identified through alternative means, e.g. through direct dialogue with stakeholders and findings from literature. In the two pilot areas, Tampere Region, Finland, and Østfold county, Norway, more detailed regional mappings were conducted, as presented below.

2.2.1. Mapping in Denmark – Material flow analysis

For Task 1.2, the material flow analysis of biobased side and waste streams in Denmark was conducted (D1.2 - to be published in 2025). Currently, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding of biobased side stream generation, treatment and disposal in Denmark. The categorization of biobased

side streams is also unclear, making it difficult to improve the treatment and utilization of these streams. The first step of material flow analysis is system definition.

The system boundary includes 13 processes related to biobased side stream generation and 5 processes related to the treatment of biobased side streams. The biobased side streams were classified into 5 main categories and 16 sub-categories. The main categories are captured manure, organic waste from crop farming, organic waste from industries, organic waste from households and sludge from wastewater treatment. The five treatment methods considered are anaerobic digestion (to produce biogas), composting, land application, incineration and landfill.

The results show that the total biobased side stream generation in Denmark amounted to 44.87 Mt in 2021. Livestock manure was the largest contributor, followed by organic side streams from crop farming. Most manure and organic waste from crop farming are applied to fields. Anaerobic digestion (AD) treated the second-largest share of biobased side streams after field application, primarily processing manure and organic waste from industries.

To predict the future trend in biobased side streams, historical data and published policies were examined to identify suitable prediction model for each sub-category. The prediction of biobased side stream generation was carried out under two scenarios: a business-as-usual (BAU) scenario and a carbon tax scenario. Meanwhile, the prediction of treatment methods was conducted under a frozen scenario and a green policy scenario.

Under the BAU scenario, total biobased side streams generation is projected to gradually increase from 44.9 Mt in 2021 to 46.3 Mt by 2050. The Danish government plans to introduce a carbon tax on agriculture in 2030, with a subsequent increase in 2035. This tax is expected to impact both livestock and crop farming. Under the carbon tax scenario, total biobased side streams generation is projected to decrease from 44.9 Mt in 2021 to 38.3 Mt by 2050. Under the green policy scenario, the proportion of biobased side streams treated with AD is projected to increase significantly, from 30% to 72%, while the amount of biobased side streams treated through incineration will gradually decline. Anaerobic digestion has emerged as a key treatment method for biobased side streams in Denmark. The forecast results of different scenarios indicate that in the future, biogas produced from the AD treatment of biobased side streams could fully meet Denmark's gas demand.

2.2.1.1. Mapping in Denmark - Value chain assessment

When it comes to Value Chain assessment, deliverable D1.2 took a top-down view of the value chain. Bio-based side-streams were analysed in a nation-wide, low-resolution value chain model in which their interactions with all other economic activities in Denmark were modelled. Results from these types of optimisation analyses present a central plan which is ideal, but can be used as a benchmark to guide decision making, and to provide insight on bottlenecks, ideal areas of investment, and so on.

The work in D1.2 looked at the economic flows between 19 industrial sectors, in five regions/locations covering Denmark. The analysis used macroeconomic statistical data to account for primary resource harvesting/mining, industrial production of goods and services, and regional consumption. Five waste categories were used, the same as in the material flow analysis model and calibrated to the physical flows using value for energy. This was all done using the Bioresource and Recycling Optimisation Model BROMo, an in-house mathematical optimisation methodology coded in the Julia programming language.

Six scenarios were simulated, where the five types of biowaste can be processed through different means by three industries: biogasification, production of manure, and power generation. In the value chain optimization model, recycling happens when the demand for outputs from the recycling industry increases, or if recycling is cheaper than the alternative non-recycled products, accounting for production capacity and transport. In the base case, where no special incentives are considered, the preferred treatment for biobased side streams is incineration with energy recovery; captured manure and biobased side streams from industry are disposed of without economic gains due to their processing costs or lack of demand for the products. In a counterfactual scenario, with increasing value of biogas and fertilizers, incineration capacity increases significantly, although treatment of sludge remains low. In both of the cases above, we noticed activity in generally all five of the locations we divided Denmark into, but interestingly, there were differences across them in timing of the activity, source of the waste streams processed, and the type of waste which was preferred.

Other simulations ran on the dataset showed how geographical location, the value of recycling outputs, amount of waste collected, and emphasis on reutilisation change the economic outlook and shape of the value chains involved in treating biobased side-streams.

2.2.2. Mapping in Finland

In 2020, 21.5 million tonnes of biobased side and waste streams were produced in Finland, with the largest streams by volume being manure, plant-based biomasses (such as side streams from fields), and biobased side streams from the food industry, while smaller quantities came from municipal biowaste, sewage sludge, and nutrient-rich industrial side streams (Ravinnekierto2030, 2020). Almost all the manure produced, up to 98% is utilized in agriculture, but as only 7.2% is processed, the majority is directly applied to fields without any processing (Luostarinen et al., 2023). The regional centralisation of livestock farms across the country has led to nutrient imbalances, with some regions having an excess of manure and others a shortage.

The processing of biomass streams such as sewage sludge, household biowaste, and by-products from the food industry is often required by legislation to mitigate their environmental impact, and most of these streams are treated at biogas plants. In contrast, only 1,5% of side streams from agriculture and the food industry are processed, with the rest being used as such (Ravinnekierto2030, 2020). This reveals opportunities for improvement, such as increasing the use of biogas plants to recover energy and enhance the utilization of recycled nutrients.

In Finland, an online service Biomass Atlas provides estimates of side streams based on national registers, such as the national field plot register, which identifies main crops grown annually (Natural Resources Institute Finland, 2024). While some data in the Biomass Atlas is updated regularly, such as annually or bi-annually, others, like the manure register, are updated less frequently. As of December 2024, the most recent manure data was from 2020. Due to a significant decrease in the number of livestock farms, which fell by more than 30% from 13 400 farms in 2020 to 9 200 farms in 2024 (Natural Resources Institute Finland, 2024b) the manure data is also likely to be quite outdated. Indicative data on side streams can be found, but it should be treated with caution. The Biomass Atlas is one of the most comprehensive online tools publicly available in the project countries.

2.2.2.1. Pirkanmaa biomass mapping

EcoFellows Ltd (EKOF) aims to promote biogas and recycled fertilizer production in Pirkanmaa (Tampere region), in cooperation with local municipalities. The biomass data from Biomass Atlas is far too uncertain to be used as a basis for planning biogas and recycled fertilizer investments in municipalities. The Biomass Atlas does give an indication of the estimated amounts of side-streams, but it is based on statistical data that do not necessarily give an accurate picture of the current situation. In addition, the statistical data are for the whole municipality and municipalities can sometimes be very large in area and long distances within a municipality. It is not profitable to transport the biomass needed by a biogas plant, such as manure and other agricultural side streams, over long distances from farms to biogas plants using current logistical means. For this reason, EKOF carried out more detailed surveys of biomass availability and locations in three municipalities in the region.

The surveys started in the summer of 2023 in the town of Mänttä-Vilppula with a questionnaire sent to farms in the area via the local authorities. However, only three responses to the questionnaire were received. For this reason, it was decided to start telephone interviews in autumn 2023. In addition to biomass data, the telephone interviews also investigated the respondents' interest in receiving recycled fertilizers and their interest in being part of a biogas cooperative of farmers. The interviews in Mänttä-Vilppula were completed in early 2024, followed by similar interviews in the town of Orivesi and Hämeenkyrö municipality during spring 2024. The interviews focused mainly on the available manure potential, but other possible side streams were also explored. Small amounts of other side streams were found, including grass and eggshells, but these were very low in overall quantities. They are therefore not listed in the table below.

Table 1. Amount of manure in pilot municipalities, tonnes.

Municipality	Statistics from Biomass Atlas (data from 2020)	TREASoURcE surveys (2023-2024)
Hämeenkyrö	57 870	35 529
Mänttä-Vilppula	14 433	8 403
Orivesi	35 809	12 359

The biomass data collected by TREASoURcE through the interviews is not a comprehensive picture of the potential of the whole municipality, as it was based on the biomass that could be found within a good logistical distance from a suitable biogas plant location.

Based on the TREASoURcE studies, the available biomass would be sufficient for the construction of a viable biogas plant in Hämeenkyrö. The biomass in Orivesi would be sufficient for a small biogas plant, but the situation would already be more uncertain than in Hämeenkyrö. In Mänttä-Vilppula, on the other hand, the studies show that the situation would not be very good for a biogas plant based on agricultural side streams.

The TREASoURcE project aims to identify opportunities for local investments in biogas plants and recycled fertilizer production and to help local actors build new bioeconomy models (T5.4). Based on the biomass surveys, work will continue in the Hämeenkyrö area together with the municipality and local farmers. Farmers are interested in setting up a joint limited company, while the cooperative was not supported in the surveys. In Mänttä-Vilppula and Orivesi, on the other hand, together with four neighbouring municipalities, the potential for a joint biogas plant for municipal wastewater treatment plants is now being investigated.

2.2.3. Mapping in Norway

Østfold generates significant amounts of bio-based side and waste streams. These streams were mapped regionally, with additional specialized models and tools used to assess (a) on-farm animal manure and (b) the bioenergy potential of field border zones.

2.2.3.1 Regional mapping of bio-based side and waste streams

This chapter summarizes the findings of a mapping study of bio-based side and waste streams in Østfold County, Norway. The study was conducted by two 4th-year MSc students in Bioeconomy at NMBU, Ingebrigt Skollerud and Sander Kleven.

The study used a variety of methods to gather data on bio-based side and waste streams in Østfold County. These methods included:

- Reviewing statistics (Statistics Norway, n.d.) (Data Norge, n.d.)
- National data from the Environment Protection Agency on emissions to air and water (Norwegian Environment Agency, n.d.)
- Reading reports, science papers, and LCA-studies (Melbye et al., 2014) (Stensgård & Callewaert, 2021) (Røsnes, 2021)
- Holding meetings with stakeholders
- Consulting with advisors from the county governor (Østfold County Governor, 2024)

The study focused on five main categories of bio-based side and waste streams:

- Agriculture (primary production, manure, slaughter waste)

- Aquaculture & Fisheries
- Forestry (logging, sawmills, buffer zones, industry)
- Industry (food processing & general industry waste)
- Municipal & District (sewage, food waste in households & different sectors)

For each mapped side and waste stream represented in the main categories, conversions and estimations of the quantities has been made on both regional and municipal level in Østfold, providing a basis and model for performing similar studies in other counties and districts.

The study found that there is a significant amount of bio-based side and waste streams generated in Østfold County. The most promising side streams for utilization were identified as:

- Straw
- Grain bran
- Animal manure
- Forestry residues (Branches, tops and roots)
- Energy potential from border zones of fields

Flow charts have been produced to show the potential utilization and business model for each of these selected side streams, demonstrating scenarios with different levels of desirability for the utilization. A flowchart for the potential utilization of straw can be seen in annex 4.

Table 2. Energy potential from selected agricultural and forestry bio-based waste, Østfold

Waste stream	Quantity (county level, tons)	Energy potential (GWh)
Straw	167 000	301
Grain bran	1 677	5
Branches, roots and tops	510 000	1 200
Buffer zones	23 400	124
Animal manure	27 000	112

The numbers related to the energy potential from the most promising bio-based side and waste streams, seen in Table 2 above, have been utilized in a public report on the energy outlook for the region of Southern Østfold comprising the municipalities of Fredrikstad, Hvaler, Sarpsborg, Halden and Aremark. The report has been shared with the corresponding regional board for political consultation between different municipalities. The findings from the report forms part of the basis for local political energy strategies and business development plans in the region.

Findings from the mapping have been made available to bio-economy research institute NORSUS and the regional biogas partnership and network Biogas Oslofjord, making it available to be used by stakeholders to identify potential sources of bio-based resources. The data will also be used to develop a decision-support tool that will help stakeholders to assess the feasibility of utilizing bio-based side and waste streams.

The mapping study of bio-based side and waste streams in Østfold County has provided valuable insights into the potential for utilizing these resources. The study has also identified some of the challenges that need to be addressed to realize this potential. The data collected from this study will be used to support the development of a more sustainable bioeconomy in Østfold County.

2.2.3.2 Map solution for mapping and visualizing biogas potential from livestock manure at farm level

In collaboration with Biogas Oslofjord, a study assessed and calculated the energy potential from Østfold farms possessing animal manure. Using publicly available livestock numbers and meat production data, along with a methodology from a Swedish handbook, (Avfall Sverige, 2009) calculations were performed. The resulting energy potential was mapped and visualized, considering the distance of each farm to existing biogas plants. The map below, focused on the Frevar biogas plant in Fredrikstad municipality, illustrates this, with green areas denoting the closest farms. Replicating this model may be difficult in countries lacking publicly accessible farm-level data.

Figure 5. Energy potential from animal manure, Østfold.

2.2.3.3 Calculation of wood chip potential near agricultural fields

The Municipality of Fredrikstad has developed the digital tool that focuses on calculating the potential volume of wood chips that can be obtained from a five-meter buffer zone along agricultural fields. The tool aims to assess how much biomass can be collected from trees within this defined area.

To conduct this analysis, different datasets were used, including the AR5 (Arealressurs, Norwegian for land resource) topological land resource map, which provides information about farmland and grass production, and the SR16 (Skogressurs, Norwegian for forest resource) forest resource map, developed by Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO), which contains data derived from satellite imagery, laser scanning, and aerial photography.

Data processing was carried out using FME (Safe feature manipulation engine) software, and the findings were visualized in an online GIS (Geographic Information System) tool as shown in Figure 6. There are plans to expand the model to include additional areas, such as those along roads and power lines, while excluding environmentally protected zones and riverbanks. Another important step involves converting the estimated cubic meters of wood chips into energy values in kilowatt-hours, which requires a better understanding of tree species and their respective energy potentials.

The methodology used in this study is relatively simple to replicate, provided that similar datasets and software are available. While most countries have topographical datasets similar to AR5, the availability of detailed biomass data like the SR16 dataset may vary. However, the same approach can be implemented using various GIS software solutions.

Figure 6. Buffer zone around farming fields. Fredrikstad Municipality

2.2.4. Mapping in Estonia

In Estonia, waste-related statistics are collected nationally (Agency, 2025). The dataset is available at the national, county, and municipal levels. This data provides insights into various bio-waste side streams, including agricultural waste, biodegradable kitchen and canteen waste, as well as garden and park waste. These statistics help to assess the volume of bio-waste generated and the opportunities for its efficient recycling.

The largest amount of bio-waste originates from animal excreta, slurry, and manure, totaling 82,269.54 tonnes annually. The second-largest category is biodegradable kitchen and canteen waste, with 34,533.89 tonnes per year. Garden and park waste ranks third, accounting for 23,084.36 tonnes annually. These three categories constitute a significant portion of Estonia's bio-waste and offer substantial potential for conversion into bioenergy or compost.

In Estonia, biodegradable kitchen and canteen waste and garden waste is mostly composted or processed into biogas. (Ecobio, 2025) biogas plant in Maardu is the only station in Estonia which handles biodegradable kitchen and canteen waste. This facility can handle approximately 20,000 tonnes of biodegradable waste annually, producing biomethane used as fuel for Tallinn's gas-powered buses.

In the compost production sector, the largest operator is Tallinna Jäätmete Taaskasutuskeskus AS (AS, 2025), located at the Jõelähtme landfill. The facility processes over 20,000 tonnes of biodegradable waste (canteen waste and garden waste) per year, resulting in about 8,000 tonnes of compost.

Agricultural waste is mainly processed in biogas (biomethane) plants, where manure and other agricultural residues are used to produce biogas. For instance, the Oisu biomethane plant (Eesti Biogaas OÜ, 2025) in Viljandi County and the Vinni biomethane plant (Eesti Biogaas OÜ, 2025) in Lääne-Viru County convert such waste into biomethane, which is used as a transport fuel.

The largest biomethane producers in Estonia include:

- **Rohegaas OÜ:** Located in Kunda, Lääne-Viru County, this plant began production in spring 2018. It produces biomethane from sewage sludge, with an annual production capacity of approximately 6 million cubic meters.
- **Biometaan OÜ:** Located in Koksvere, Viljandi County, this plant started production in summer 2018. It produces biomethane from cow slurry, silage, and manure, processing 81,000 tons of slurry, 5,000 tons of solid manure, and 5,000 tons of silage per year, with an annual production capacity of around 3 million cubic meters.
- **Vinni Biogas OÜ:** Located in Vinni, Lääne-Viru County, this plant started biomethane production in 2020. It produces biomethane from agricultural substrates and plays a significant role in Estonia's biomethane industry.
- **Tartu Biogas OÜ:** Located in Ilmatsalu, Tartu County, this plant also began biomethane production in 2020. Similar to Vinni Biogas, it processes agricultural substrates to produce biomethane.

- **Oisu Biogas OÜ:** Located in Järva County, this plant started biomethane production in 2021. It utilizes agricultural waste to produce biomethane, contributing to Estonia's renewable energy sector.

Additionally, new biomethane plants are planned. HKScan Estonia and Bioforce Production are planning to build Estonia's largest agricultural biomethane plant in Viljandi County, with an annual production capacity of 7–8 million cubic meters. The plant is expected to be completed by the end of 2025.

In summary, Estonia has several companies and facilities dedicated to processing various biodegradable waste streams, transforming them into valuable resources such as biomethane and compost.

2.2.4.1. Additional research

The Environmental Portal provides a comprehensive overview of bio-waste in Estonia, including requirements for separate collection, processing options, and statistics. The page explains the importance of bio-waste, such as kitchen and canteen waste, garden and park waste, and agricultural residues, in the circular economy. It also highlights how bio-waste management helps reduce landfill disposal and supports the production of biogas and compost. Information on bio-waste management in Estonia, including collection requirements, processing methods, and statistics, can be found from Keskkonnaagentuur's web page (Keskkonnaagentuur, 2024).

Over the years, Estonia has conducted several studies to assess its biomass resources and biogas production potential. Between 2016 and 2021, a private initiative mapped the generation of gardening biowaste across the country, resulting in a publicly available story map, that provides detailed insights into the distribution and volume of such waste (Taraskin, 2023)

In preparation for the Estonian Energy Development Plan until 2035 (Energiaatlgud, 2022), comprehensive studies were undertaken to evaluate the nation's biogas potential. These analyses, primarily based on data from 2010 to 2015, identified key biomass streams suitable for significant biogas production, including animal manure, agricultural green mass, and sewage sludge. Biowaste was also recognized as a supportive feedstock in this context.

Recent research by the Estonian University of Life Sciences highlights that a substantial amount of biodegradable waste, particularly in southeastern Estonia, remains unutilized for biogas production. This underscores the untapped potential within the country's bioeconomy (Kersa, 2023).

Furthermore, Estonia's abundant forest coverage positions it as a significant player in the European bioenergy market. With over 50% of its land covered by forests, the nation is among the largest biomass suppliers in the EU. Advanced digitization and the cascaded use of biomass ensure transparency and sustainability in the utilization of these resources.

2.3. Stakeholder mapping

The stakeholder mapping was conducted in collaboration with WP2 T2.1 “Establishment of structures for stakeholder engagement” to provide a structured foundation for stakeholder involvement throughout the project. The objective was to identify key actors within the ecosystem who play a role in CE transitions, biobased side and waste stream valorisation, and nutrient recovery.

The mapping was documented in a shared Excel sheet, including details such as stakeholder names, locations, roles, relevance to stakeholder engagement, and their connection to the project's key value chains (KVCs). The mapping was conducted by project partners from Estonia, Finland and Norway, separately for each country. The purpose of this structured approach was to enable targeted engagement and collaboration across different value chain phases.

Table 3 presents the numbers of stakeholders identified in relation to WP5, altogether 591. All these WP5 actors were divided by their connection to each separate section of the value chain model created (Figure 3). Based on the value chain model it was decided to focus on the actors other than consumers and producers of biobased side and waste streams. This was because private persons, such as individual farmers or forest owners, were not considered important to identify on an individual level. The focus on the categorization was on larger-scale industry and policy-level actors who could drive systemic change in circular bioeconomy solutions.

In relation to WP5 special attention was given to:

- Processing and refining of bio-based side and waste streams
- Nutrient and material recovery
- Biogas utilization
- Market and distribution actors
- National and EU-level stakeholders

Table 3. Stakeholders identified in the stakeholder mapping for bio KVC with WP2.

All categories	Side stream production	Processing & refining of materials	Nutrient & material refining	Biogas utilization	Market & distribution	National level & EU
591	230	91	48	46	20	128

In addition, the project created digital visualizations for the Finnish stakeholders for the three value chains: bio, plastics, and EV batteries (Figure 7). These visualizations follow the same structure as Figure 3, displaying the categories and the specific stakeholders associated with them, as identified in the study. The interactive visualizations can be accessed at [TREASoURcE Stakeholder Mapping](#) (TREASoURcE, 2023d).

Figure 7. Stakeholder mapping for the value chain models of bio-based side and waste streams.

The stakeholder mapping serves as a foundation for engagement efforts in the project by establishing a structured and systematic approach to identifying relevant actors within the bio-based CE. By defining key stakeholders and their roles early in the project, the mapping enabled a more targeted and effective collaboration process, ensuring engagement activities to be directed toward those who can contribute most significantly to the project's objectives. Furthermore, the mapping strengthened cooperation between WP5 and key stakeholders in nutrient recovery, bio-based refining, and biogas utilization, thereby facilitating the development of viable CE solutions.

By categorizing stakeholders based on their position in the key value chains, the mapping enhanced the ability to align project activities with real-world industry and policy dynamics. The mapping remains a dynamic tool in the project, although mostly used in the first third of the project, it has continuously been updated to reflect the evolving stakeholder landscape.

2.3.1. Bio refineries and industries utilizing biobased side and waste streams

The use of biobased side and waste streams is expanding across various industries, promoting resource efficiency and supporting the CE. These streams, ranging from crop residues and processing by-products to manure and organic waste, serve as valuable raw materials for multiple sectors. Given the project's scope and objectives, this chapter examines biorefineries and industries utilizing these resources.

Industries such as biogas production, recycled fertilizer manufacturing, and biorefineries already make significant use of agricultural side streams. These sectors rely on organic residues and nutrient-rich materials to generate energy, produce fertilizers, and create bio-based chemicals and fuels. Meanwhile, emerging applications in industries like cosmetics, packaging, and textiles hold potential for higher value uses, which could increase the market value of agricultural side streams and generate additional income for primary producers. For example, bioactive compounds extracted from agricultural residues could be used in natural cosmetics, while biodegradable packaging solutions could reduce reliance on fossil-based materials.

Table 4. Key industries utilizing biobased side and waste streams.

Industry	Examples of the biobased side and waste streams utilized
Alcohol industry	Uses agricultural residues for fermentation and bioethanol production.
Biochar production	Converts biomass residues into soil-improving carbon products.
Biogas plants	Digest organic materials to produce renewable energy and digestate.
Biorefineries	Process several types of streams into bio-based chemicals, fuels, and materials.
Building industry	Uses biobased construction materials, e.g. straw-based insulation.
Chemical industry	Develops biobased alternatives for solvents, polymers, and coatings.
Cosmetics industry & natural products	Utilizes plant-based ingredients and agricultural extracts for beauty and wellness products.
Energy industry	Converts agricultural residues into biomass fuels, bio-oils, and biofuels.
Food and feed industries	Repurpose processing by-products for animal feed and food additives.
Other specialty products	Develops innovative biobased applications, such as adhesives or biodegradable plastics.
Paper and packaging industry	Uses agricultural fibres as sustainable raw materials for paper, cardboard, and bioplastics.
Pharmaceutical industry	Extracts bioactive compounds from agricultural side streams for medicinal applications.
Recycled fertilizer producers	Process organic waste into nutrient-rich fertilizers.
Soil amendment producers	Create organic soil improvers from agricultural residues.
Textile and fibre industry	Utilizes agricultural side streams for sustainable fabrics.
Alcohol industry	Uses agricultural residues for fermentation and bioethanol production.

While many biobased side and waste streams are already utilized in energy and fertilizer production, there is growing potential to direct these materials toward higher-value applications. Developing new biobased products, such as advanced biomaterials, high-value chemicals, and specialty ingredients, can significantly increase the economic returns for primary producers. Many of these innovations are still in the research and development phase, but with continued investment and scaling efforts, they could transition into full-scale industrial production in the coming years. Encouraging the use of side streams in high-value applications ensures that raw material suppliers, including farmers, forest owners and processors, could benefit from improved profitability, making circular bioeconomy solutions more attractive across the supply chain.

Expanding the utilization of biobased side streams into higher-value products will require targeted investments, innovation, and policy support to overcome current barriers related to supply chain logistics, seasonal availability, and cost-efficiency. The digital marketplace, [KiertoaSuomesta.fi](https://kiertoasuomesta.fi), presented in Chapter 3 is the TREASoURcE project's initiative to promote the market development by offering available resources to the industry actors as well.

In addition, biorefineries play a crucial role in rural areas by creating new jobs, stimulating economic and social development, and supporting local employment through their proximity to crop production sites, making them a key element in strengthening the biobased economy (Lange et al., 2021).

To gain a deeper understanding of how different industries utilize and procure biobased side and waste streams, industry stakeholders were contacted through phone calls and face-to-face meetings. Insights from these discussions, including key challenges are presented in Chapter 2.7: Challenges identified and most potential side and waste streams for future use.

2.4. Cooperative models

The work in T5.4 “Powering local economies through circular bioeconomy” has largely focused on exploring suitable organizational models for initiating joint biorefineries, including biogas plants and recycled fertilizer production. The aim is to promote the use of the biobased side and waste streams and to create new business opportunities for the value chain. These models include cooperatives, limited liability companies, and, in certain cases, producer organizations, depending on the context and requirements. An example of the concept for the cooperative model is presented in Figure 4.

Regardless of the chosen cooperative model, emphasis has been placed on the economic and fertilizer-related benefits of digestate as the key factors influencing farmer participation. The specific organizational structure, whether a cooperative or limited liability company, is often seen as secondary. Ultimately, the focus is on ensuring income generation and economic viability for participants, reinforcing the importance of collaborative models in advancing sustainability and profitability in agriculture. In some cases, instead of direct revenue, the economic benefit comes from reduced costs. Below some possibilities are briefly described.

2.4.1. Cooperative and limited company

When farmers consider setting up a joint initiative for a biogas plant, the choice between a cooperative and a limited company depends on their objectives and operational priorities. A cooperative is typically member-driven, with profits distributed among members based on their contribution, fostering equality and shared decision-making. It is well-suited for farmers aiming to pool resources, prioritize mutual benefits, and maintain collective control. In contrast, a limited company operates as a profit-oriented entity, where decision-making is often proportional to ownership shares. This structure is more flexible for attracting external investors and managing risks, as liabilities are limited to the extent of the invested capital. While cooperatives emphasize collaboration and shared benefits, limited companies offer a more structured framework for scaling operations and accessing broader financial resources. The choice ultimately depends on the farmers' goals, financial strategies, and the level of external involvement they seek.

The farmers who responded to the biomass surveys in Pirkanmaa for T5.4 were asked also about their interest in a joint biogas enterprise, and there was plenty of interest. Cooperation allows the risks of investment to be shared between several actors and, on the other hand, the possibility of sharing the additional workload of the plant is also of interest to farmers. The respondents highlighted interest towards a limited company, instead of a cooperative. The reasons for choosing this option were not asked in detail in the surveys, but some respondents mentioned that decision-making is easier in a limited company.

2.4.2. Producer organization

Collaboration on new cooperative models has been undertaken with MTK's Tuotto project (2022–2024) and its continuation, the Tuovi project, starting in 2025. These initiatives aim to promote producer organizations for agricultural products by engaging farmers and stakeholders in collaborative efforts. The focus is on identifying interested farmers, supporting established producer organizations, and fostering networking and collaboration on a national scale. This approach seeks to create additional revenue streams for farmers through joint business models and cooperative initiatives.

In the context of biogas plants, the potential for producer organizations to coordinate farmers supplying feedstock has been considered. The regulatory perspective needs to be fully addressed. Competition law prohibits farmers from jointly discussing input prices, such as those for fertilizers or digestate from biogas plants, unless the prices are publicly available, to prevent anti-competitive behaviour. These regulations also limit opportunities for joint procurement of production inputs. These challenges could be tackled by setting up a joint producer organization which enables joint procurement and price setting for farmers. However, current rules restrict producer organizations to food-related agricultural products, complicating the formation of producer organizations for non-food chains like biogas feedstock.

Despite the challenges, producer organizations hold potential for optimizing supply chains, fostering collaboration, and enabling collective bargaining. Addressing regulatory and legal barriers will be essential to unlock their full potential in supporting CE initiatives.

2.4.3. Collaboration with municipalities

Municipalities can play a crucial role in promoting the development of jointly owned biogas plants, such as those co-owned by farmers. They can act as initiators by providing consulting assistance, offering land, and facilitating biomass assessments. By offering consulting assistance, municipalities can guide stakeholders through the complex process of establishing a biogas plant. This includes providing expertise on regulatory requirements, financial planning, and technical aspects of biogas production. In addition, municipalities can help to find suitable land for biogas plants and ensure that suitable sites are available for these plants.

Facilitating biomass assessments is another critical role that municipalities can undertake. By conducting thorough assessments of available biomass resources, municipalities can help identify potential feedstocks for biogas production. This information is essential for planning and optimizing the operation of biogas plants.

When considering the role of municipalities, the advantages and challenges of their participation in a cooperative or limited company should be carefully evaluated. Municipal involvement can influence funding possibilities, as their role and obligations may differ from those of other organizations.

Moreover, municipalities can actively promote the development of biogas projects by creating demand for biogas. This can be achieved by encouraging local industries, public transportation systems, and other entities to utilize biogas as an energy source. The examples of Nokia, Vieremä and Tallinn illustrate how municipalities can successfully foster demand for biogas, thereby supporting the viability and sustainability of biogas projects. These examples along with aspects on how municipalities can promote the use of biobased resources through procurement are discussed in Chapter 3.4. Public procurement promoting the use of biobased resources.

2.5 Østfold's mobile solution

The need and best possible solution for a mobile composting or biogas unit for rent by stakeholders like upper secondary schools and event organizers/festivals were started by the county of Viken and continued and finished by the County of Østfold following the demerge of the County of Viken. The purpose was to examine the need and potential for circular measures and uses for food waste from schools and festivals/events, for instance demonstrating processing of food waste from festivals into nutrient-rich soils and soil improvers that event organizers could provide or sell to visitors at the festival.

2.5.1. Findings from preliminary mapping and market inquiries

A preliminary mapping showed that mobile biogas units were unavailable and current mobile biogas fuel stations would be too costly to be suitable for rental purposes. It was then decided to proceed with a market inquiry on available mobile solutions for composting of food waste to tailor minimum requirements and criteria for an eventual procurement of a mobile unit.

Parameters covered by the market inquiry included loss of nutrients, like phosphorus and nitrogen, emissions to air from the processing, calculated climate gains, investment and operational costs as well as expected longevity and feasibility of operating the unit.

A European-wide market inquiry, using a request for information, was done, but this inquiry did not yield any responses. Ordering a market assessment from the Norwegian University of Life Science of a selection of current national and regional providers of composting units, a set of criteria was evaluated to determine which supplier could provide the best fit of circular effects/solutions and costs. One provider, Biocotech, stood out from the others, having a documented and national authority approved solution for hygienization of the residual product from the composting unit.

2.5.2. Findings and assessments from inquiries with selected providers

Subsequent dialogue and inquiries with the selected providers on leasing arrangements and ordinary procurement of a mobile solution for a composting unit as well as options with and without a tailor-made trailer solution to transport the unit yielded the following main findings:

- Current market options for composting units for food waste are still mainly made for stationary location and the market for mobile solutions is highly immature
- Innovation costs for a mobile solution are high, ranging from 48 570 – 51 850 Euro (value added tax excluded), requiring a significant market uptake to cover or justify procurement costs
- Current providers lack a logistical infrastructure for a rental solution. Energy requirements and operational requirements for a mobile solution for festivals can also still represent an impediment for some event organizers.

2.5.3 Concluding assessments

There are several suppliers of industrial composting machinery, but current business and technical operational models for these are geared towards stationary solutions. Financial costs for adapting a mobile solution and operational/logistical requirements to utilize a mobile solution for the possible procuring stakeholders indicate a very limited market for rental solutions for mobile composting units for events and schools.

2.6 Fredrikstad’s new post-sorting and treatment plants’ value chains and logistics

Fredrikstad’s new post-sorting and treatment plant – ØAS (in Norwegian Østfold Avfallssortering IKS) is a public inter-municipal company dedicated to transforming waste management practices across Østfold County in Norway. This initiative aligns with the EU’s increasingly stringent waste management and recycling directives, providing a framework to meet both current needs and future scalability.

ØAS represents a collaborative effort between several municipalities, including Fredrikstad, Sarpsborg, Halden, Rakkestad, Hvaler, and MOVAR IKS, which comprises Moss, Råde, Våler, and Vestby. The value chain of Fredrikstad’s facility begins with the collection of household waste from these participating municipalities which have approximately 267,000 residents and generate 50,400 tons of waste annually (as of 2022). This waste is primarily composed of residual waste streams, which the new facility will process.

The sorting operations utilize advanced technologies, including shredding for bag opening, mechanical sorting and NIR technology to segregate recyclable materials such as plastics, metals, and paper. These materials then enter separate value chains tailored to their specific recycling or recovery processes.

Figure 8. Visualization of ØAS operation.

By isolating and channelling each material into dedicated value chains, the facility maximizes the amount of sorted out material going to recovery and recycling operations in other sites, reduces waste sent to landfills, and aligns with Norway’s circular economy goals.

2.6.1. Challenges in scaling up of production

Fredrikstad's post-sorting and treatment plant faces a range of interconnected challenges that must be addressed to ensure the successful scaling and operation of its facilities. One significant obstacle is the delay in the approval of regulations for Viken Park, which has postponed the project's initiation.

However, this regulatory milestone was achieved in December 2024, with Fredrikstad Municipality granting its approval. The construction of the facility is now scheduled to commence in the second half of 2026, marking a significant step forward in the project's timeline.

A critical aspect of scaling up operations involves overcoming value chain challenges. A key priority is ensuring the quality of input waste streams, which is essential for maintaining high recovery rates. Improperly source separated materials, such as batteries mixed into residual waste streams, present significant safety and operational risks. For instance, batteries can cause fires during processing, highlighting the need for stringent detection and removal measures to mitigate these hazards. Public awareness campaigns and standardized waste collection practices help mitigate contamination issues.

The facility also faces challenges in securing stable markets for delivery of the sorted materials. Fluctuations in demand for paper and cardboard can directly impact profitability, emphasizing the need for robust market analysis and diversification strategies to manage these economic risks.

Regulatory compliance adds another layer of complexity. The plant must navigate evolving legislation around producer responsibility and waste management practices, ensuring that its operations align with both legal and user requirements.

2.6.2. Opportunities for optimization and scale-up

Despite these challenges, ØAS also presents numerous opportunities for optimization and growth. Collaboration among the municipalities that own and operate ØAS offers a chance to create more harmonized and efficient waste management systems, improving overall material quality and reducing operational redundancies. Expanding the plant's capacity by accepting waste deliveries from additional municipalities and private actors can significantly increase tonnage, maximizing the facility's usage and economic viability. Another key opportunity is the reduction of CO₂ emissions, and its related costs achieved by extracting plastics from the waste stream for incineration, which contributes to lower emissions and aligns with climate targets. Additionally, the ØAS is planning for solar panels and investigating the installation of a battery bank opens opportunities to manage energy more sustainably and reduce the cost of operating the facility by reducing peaks and overall power consumption from the grid.

2.7. Challenges identified and future innovations for more efficient use of side streams

The utilization of biobased side and waste streams presents significant opportunities for improving resource efficiency and promoting CE principles, as presented in previous chapters. However, insights gathered throughout the project, through various events, workshops, and stakeholder meetings, have highlighted multiple challenges that hinder large-scale adoption. Discussions with industry representatives, primary producers, researchers, and sectoral organizations have provided a comprehensive view of the barriers related to procurement processes, logistical constraints, and regulatory issues.

Biogas producers, recycled fertilizer manufacturers, and biochar producers were engaged through phone calls and face-to-face meetings to assess the feasibility of integrating biobased materials from agriculture into industrial operations. In fall 2024, an assessment was conducted to evaluate the potential of side streams from an industry perspective, further refining the understanding of key challenges and opportunities. These discussions also helped identify potential solutions, such as improving supply chain coordination and developing shared processing infrastructure. Furthermore, engagement with stakeholders aimed to raise awareness of the digital marketplace (see Chapter 3) and gather feedback from different actors on its suitability as a tool for facilitating side stream exchange.

Several key challenges have been identified:

- **Profitability and cost structure** – The economic viability of utilizing agricultural side streams remains a major issue. Many side streams have low or unstable market value, making it difficult for businesses to justify investments in collection, processing, and transport. Without stronger incentives or market-driven demand, side stream utilization remains secondary to more established production chains.
- **Logistical challenges** – Agricultural side streams are geographically fragmented, often produced in small volumes across dispersed farms. Transporting and centralizing them for processing can be expensive and inefficient. The seasonal nature of plant-based side streams further complicates logistics, as materials become available in large quantities only during short harvest periods, leading to bottlenecks in storage and distribution. Joint collection and regional processing hubs could help optimize logistics, but their implementation requires coordination and investment.
- **The regulatory framework** - A long list of regulations governs the collection, storage, and processing of biobased materials adding further challenges to their efficient utilization. Also, the definition of waste remains unclear in some cases. The regulatory framework has been considered complex by the sectors operators, especially from the perspective of regulatory uncertainties and policy instability:
 - Unpredictable policymaking – Frequent changes in regulations create instability, making long-term investments in CE solutions risky. More detailed analysis of these policy challenges is provided in D1.3 Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains (TREASoURcE, 2024).

- **Perceptions towards human-derived nutrient recycling** – The use of sewage sludge-derived nutrients is hindered by social resistance and strict industry policies. Many food companies refuse to accept crops fertilized with human-based nutrients, limiting the market potential of this nutrient source. Despite technological advancements in nutrient recovery, public perception and food safety concerns remain a major challenge.
- **Quality concerns in recycled fertilizers** – Concerns over the safety of waste-based fertilizers have been presented due to findings of, for example, plastic contamination in fertilizers produced from biowaste sources. The presence of microplastics raises long-term risks for soil contamination and food safety, further complicating public acceptance and regulatory approval for these products. Addressing these issues will require stricter quality control measures, improved processing technologies, and clearer regulatory guidelines.
- **Lack of awareness about the potential of side streams** – Some stakeholders, such as certain farmers, do not consider the possibility that their side streams could be valuable to others. This may be due to a lack of information or the assumption that there is no demand. While in some cases this may be true, increasing awareness and encouraging these actors to explore potential uses and markets for their side streams is crucial for improving resource efficiency and fostering new business opportunities.
- **Limited manure utilization in crop farms** – Although mapping efforts have highlighted manure as a valuable nutrient source, its use remains largely confined to livestock farms. Crop farms face multiple obstacles in adopting manure-based fertilizers:
 - Technical challenges – Organic fertilizers, including manure and recycled fertilizers often require specialized spreading equipment, which many crop farms do not have. In addition, they might behave differently in soil compared to mineral fertilizers.
 - Behavioural and social factors – Many crop farms rely on mineral fertilizers due to their ease of use, uniform composition, and established application practices. Transitioning to fertilizers made from recycled origin, would require changes in farm management and mindset.

→ While the digital marketplace (see Chapter 3) has been promoted as a tool to connect manure suppliers with crop farmers, adoption has been slow due to these barriers.
- **Low profitability of agriculture** - The weak position of farmers in the food chain and low agricultural profitability have reduced investment capacity on farms. This limits the adoption of new technologies and infrastructure needed for utilizing biobased side and waste streams, making certain CE solutions inaccessible to many primary producers.

The challenges faced were widely also discussed in the TREASoURcE workshop on bottlenecks in agriculture on 31st of October 2023, in Tampere, organized in collaboration with T2.2.4 "Symbiotic B2B partnerships". Solutions considered in the event included, for instance, coordination of collection

systems, where farms pool their side streams to improve economic viability. One operator coordinating the system and funding for the system would be needed. Support from local municipalities or national policies were seen potential to further facilitate systemic development and infrastructure investments, thereby enhancing overall effectiveness and sustainability.

One aspect raised in promoting the use of biobased resources, digestate and recycled fertiliser is the benefit of adding organic matter to the soil. There is currently no common monetary value set for increasing soil organic matter, although there are clear benefits for soil quality and crop production. Such a value could encourage the use of recycled materials and increase the value of the biobased side and waste streams.

While biobased side and waste streams hold great potential, the sector faces economic, logistical, regulatory, and social challenges that hinder widespread adoption. Strengthening collaborations between primary producers, processors, and policymakers will be essential in addressing these barriers. Additionally, continued innovation in logistics, processing technologies, and policy frameworks will be crucial in unlocking the full potential of these resources for future industrial applications.

2.7.1. New innovations to promote use of biobased side streams

While numerous challenges hinder the widespread adoption of biobased side and waste streams, several high-potential materials have been identified for further development and commercialization. Advances in processing technologies and logistics solutions are opening new opportunities for utilizing agricultural residues in more efficient and economically viable ways. As found in the mappings conducted, there remains huge potential in more efficient use of biobased side and waste streams. Hybrid solutions, which combine processing and logistics innovations, appear particularly promising, as they address both profitability constraints and transportation challenges. These solutions focus on onsite processing, reducing transportation costs and improving the usability of biobased materials directly at the source.

Among the emerging innovations, two hybrid solutions have been developed to improve the circularity and economic feasibility of manure and slurry-based side streams:

- **ManPas hygieniser** is designed by IPFur Consulting Oy for small-scale, onsite use, the device processes horse manure into hygienised material at a rate of 1.5 m³ per week. Utilizing a rapid hygienisation technique, the device heats the manure to 70°C for one hour, aligning with the EU by-product regulation. This process transforms manure into a valuable, marketable product that can be used as a soil improver or animal bedding. With a total processing time of 1 to 4 days, the ManPas device promotes self-sufficient circularity by enabling livestock farms to recycle manure into useful materials directly on-site. (HAMK, n.d.)
- **Mobile separator unit by Ruthon Services** offers an innovative service for farms, biogas plants, municipal operators, and the forest industry. Their custom-built mobile separation unit, mounted on a truck bed processes slurry-based materials at a rate of 50–150 cubic meters

per hour, depending on the material. The unit typically extracts 20–30% dry matter from slurry. The mobile separation service is delivered directly to locations where slurry is generated. On average, one site processes approximately 2,000 cubic meters of material over two days. After separation, the dry fraction is ready for field application, while the liquid fraction is stored in the client's own tanks. This service addresses challenges in nutrient recycling by providing an efficient, on-site solution for processing slurry into components that can be directly reused or transported with improved logistics. (Ruthon Services, 2025)

These innovations demonstrate how technology and logistics improvements can enhance the economic feasibility of biobased side stream utilization. By processing materials closer to the source, they reduce transportation costs, improve nutrient management, and create new market opportunities for agricultural side streams. Continued investment in hybrid processing solutions and policy support will be essential in unlocking the full potential of these materials.

3 CREATING MARKETS AND E-MARKET FOR ORGANIC SIDE STREAMS

The effective use of side streams has been slowed down by challenges related to profitability and logistics. On an individual farm, the quantities of side streams can be small and/or seasonal and suitable buyers have not been found. To address these challenges and connect supply with demand, the KiertoaSuomesta.fi (CircularFinland in English) digital marketplace was created, providing a meeting point for sellers and buyers of these materials to promote their more efficient and sustainable use.

The main target groups for the marketplace are companies in agriculture, forestry, and the food industry producing biobased side and waste streams, as well as industry and the public sector that use these raw materials. The uniqueness of the platform lies in its ability to connect all stakeholders of the value chain, as visualized in Figure 9 (complete value chain presented in Figure 3). The KiertoaSuomesta.fi platform has been developed to be the central platform for the biobased side streams, bringing together geographically dispersed producers and potential buyers in Finland.

The digital marketplace can be accessed at [KiertoaSuomesta.fi](https://kiertoasuomesta.fi) (KiertoaSuomesta, 2024).

Use of the platform is free of charge, and users can register with an email address and a business ID. The primary language of the site is Finnish, but it is also possible to change the language into Swedish or English from the top right corner of the site.

Figure 9. The stakeholders connected through KiertoaSuomesta.fi platform.

The KiertoaSuomesta.fi service has several objectives:

- **Promoting circular economy:** The platform facilitates the development of regional nutrient and material cycles, reducing the reliance on synthetic fertilizers and imported raw materials. This strengthens resource efficiency and supports climate goals by lowering greenhouse gas emissions.
- **Creating new business opportunities:** It aims to create new types of business and income opportunities for primary producers, farms especially, by enabling them to monetize their side streams more easily.
- **Improving knowledge:** Training and information materials have been developed to increase understanding of circular practices and inspire users to adopt solutions for more efficient use of resources.

One key aspect of the marketplace is its potential to foster the development of the side stream market, which is still in its early stages. By providing a platform where supply and demand can meet, it supports the emergence of a functioning market. Additionally, the marketplace contributes to the determination of the market value of these side streams, a challenge due to the lack of established benchmarks for prices.

Furthermore, the marketplace promotes environmental and climate benefits by reducing waste and increasing the recycling of nutrients, which enhances the sustainability of production systems. These actions also contribute to national security of supply and self-sufficiency by reducing dependence on imported raw materials and supporting the efficient use of local resources.

3.1 Launch and progress after the launch

The digital marketplace, KiertoaSuomesta.fi, was launched in May 2023. The work conducted for the development and launch was reported in [D5.1 Digital marketplace](#) (TREASoURcE, 2023c). In the report the background research prior to the launch is introduced, such as the stakeholder engagement activities; questionnaires and interviews conducted to gather user feedback.

Since the launch, significant efforts have been made to enhance the platform's usability and expand its features to better meet the needs of diverse stakeholders. New functionalities have been introduced to improve the user experience, and significant resources have been invested in marketing the platform to potential users, in particular farmers and other business actors in the agricultural and circular bioeconomy sectors.

Despite this progress, user acquisition has proved challenging. Farmers have shown scepticism towards adopting new digital tools, and for example fatigue from navigating multiple platforms or concerns about their utility. Additionally, awareness of CE and the potential of side streams remained low among many stakeholders, requiring educational efforts and trust-building initiatives. A key early-stage challenge has been the lack of sufficient supply and demand on the platform, leading to doubts about

its functionality. Achieving a critical mass of users is essential for the platform to gain traction and be perceived as a credible marketplace. External factors, such as low agricultural profitability, inflation, and the ongoing market instability following the ongoing war of aggression in Ukraine, have further complicated engagement efforts by farmers to explore new practices or tools.

Feedback from stakeholders has highlighted conflicting expectations: while farmers prefer straightforward and intuitive listing features, industrial actors seek more detailed and customizable options. Balancing these demands has required active collaboration with both groups.

At the time of the Deliverable 5.4 submission, the marketplace has not yet reached its full potential in terms of user activity and transaction volume, which poses challenges for replication. Nonetheless, efforts to replicate the platform's model have been explored in Norway and Estonia, with replication activities carried out in Estonia.

3.1.1. Technological development

The KiertoaSuomesta.fi platform has undergone continuous development to enhance usability, expand functionalities, and address emerging challenges. The core focus has been on improving the marketplace's effectiveness, increasing knowledge-sharing, and integrating solutions to support the circulation of biobased side streams.

One example of these developments is categorization features, which make it easier for users to search for specific materials, especially once the number of listings increases. However, while this represents a useful refinement, it is only a small part of the broader development efforts. The platform has required constant maintenance and technical adjustments.

Another key development area has been ensuring the safety and compliance of listed materials. Specific measures have been introduced, particularly regarding manure and other animal-based residues, to ensure that users posting or browsing listings acknowledge and comply with national regulations governing their handling and use. To facilitate this, automatic links to relevant regulations (e.g., manure processing and animal by-product regulations) were implemented to appear alongside related listings. Another regulatory aspect is compliance with the EU Marketplace Act, due to which statistical analysis was not included on the site, to avoid heavy reporting obligations.

Recognizing the need to increase awareness about agricultural side streams, a completely new section was developed alongside the KiertoaSuomesta.fi marketplace. MTK created this separate WordPress-based website, which was integrated to KiertoaSuomesta.fi website, to provide easily accessible information and additional features. Development began in autumn 2023 and continued throughout 2024, with MTK maintaining and continuously updating the WordPress site. The main result of this development was the content pages created to which articles were produced about CE, side streams, circular practices and nutrient recycling, for example (see Figure 9). Most of the articles were written in Finnish, but many have been translated also into English and Swedish, with 14 articles available in

English. Examples of the articles are presented in Figure 10. These efforts will be continued to share information about side streams.

The content pages aim to educate stakeholders about the benefits of utilizing agricultural side streams. The integration of the WordPress site with the KiertoaSuomesta.fi marketplace allows users to access a wealth of information and resources, facilitating the trading of side streams and fostering collaboration among farmers, industries, and municipalities.

Figure 10. The content page articles include information mainly about CE and agriculture.

Currently, the KiertoaSuomesta.fi platform includes the following components:

- **Landing page/homepage** – Provides an overview of the platform, recent updates, and information about key partners.
- **Marketplace** – Hosts actual listings of available side streams, facilitating connections between suppliers and potential users.
- **Information section** – Offers background details on the platform’s purpose and functionality. It also includes instructions on how to make a listing and a Q&A section.
- **Content pages** – Developed specifically to raise awareness about side stream utilization. These pages are categorized into four main categories: agriculture, processing industry, food industry, and public sector actors. Articles are published for each section, with a primary focus on agriculture.

By developing this comprehensive website, the aim is to increase the engagement and knowledge among farmers and other stakeholders, encouraging them to explore the opportunities that side stream utilization can offer. In the long term, the aim is to establish KiertoaSuomesta.fi as the key platform for agricultural CE, providing a centralized hub for diverse information and resources. While the primary target group is primary producers, the platform also seeks to reach businesses and public sector actors, fostering broader collaboration and knowledge-sharing. The site continues to be updated and expanded, ensuring its relevance and effectiveness in supporting the transition toward a more circular agricultural sector.

3.1.1.1. Logistics solutions and student collaboration

To enhance the marketplace's functionality, logistics service was being developed to provide an option for users to ease the logistics, one of the main hindrances in utilizing side streams. Listings for logistics and contracting services can already be listed to the marketplace, but this would allow for a more integrated approach to managing transportation needs for side stream trade.

In spring 2023, computing science student group from the University of Helsinki developed a separate logistics platform as a project course for their studies. This platform was designed to enable logistics service providers to list their services and allow side stream sellers and buyers to tender transportation services. The system was built to calculate distances, estimated costs (adjustable by logistics operators), and CO₂ emissions. API (Application Programming Interface) connections were developed between the logistics platform and KiertoaSuomesta.fi, allowing seamless data transfer.

After the student course ended, there was still some finalising work left to be done to integrate the logistics solution to the marketplace. Budget constraints prevented further development, and at the time of this report's publication, the logistics platform has not yet been launched, although additional funding has been applied for. However, efforts will continue to finalise and publish the logistics platform, as it remains a highly relevant tool for improving the efficiency of side stream transactions.

3.1.1.2. Challenges experienced

While the platform has seen significant improvements, budget limitations have restricted the full realization of planned features. The budget allocated to the technological development in the TREASoURcE project was not sufficient to cover all intended functionalities, particularly finalising and launching the logistics section. Additional technological development would have been useful, such as automated and targeted communication and marketing from the site to registered users, for example. Funding opportunities are being explored to ensure the continuation of this work.

Given the limited number of users on the KiertoaSuomesta.fi platform, it was decided that it would be unfeasible to expand the service to consumers at this stage. The platform has been specifically designed for businesses, with access requiring a business ID for login. This structure ensures that business operation is secure without sharing private information, such as addresses and contact details,

which is particularly important for some users. To maintain privacy, we've focused on offering this protection, ensuring that such personal data is not publicly displayed. Instead of pursuing a B2C approach, an approach was shifted to focus on targeting associations. These organizations, such as those managing allotment gardens, can utilize the platform collectively, leveraging its functionality to meet their needs. This adjustment allows us to focus on a user base that aligns with the platform's current scale and ensures data privacy remains a top priority.

Already before the launch of the platform, engagement with stakeholders revealed key challenges. CE and the concept of side streams were not well known by practitioners, including farmers, and the market value of side streams was unclear. Low agricultural profitability, inflation, and the energy crisis further seemed to impact farmers' openness to new ideas, such as digital solutions or circular practices. Scepticism towards new technologies and fatigue with learning to use multiple platforms were also identified. In addition, conflicting expectations emerged: farmers prefer simple listings, while industry representatives seek detailed postings. Wide collaboration with all target groups was considered essential and therefore has been continued throughout the project to both raise awareness of the platform and to tackle the challenges found.

3.1.2. Marketing of the digital marketplace

Several different events have been organized and participated in to disseminate information about the marketplace. These include seminars, webinars, meetings, workshops, field days and exhibitions days. Active communication through different channels has also been done, including building up and updating social media channels, several newsletters, articles in magazines and in a newspaper, website texts, Christmas calendar and printed brochures disseminated in events. Marketing materials are presented in Annex 1.

Table 5. Key events, in which *KiertoaSuomesta.fi* has been presented, on-site events in Finland.

Event name	Place	Organizer	Date
Developing business activities with the help of CE and data -seminar	Tampere, Finland	MTK	30.5.2023
Okra -agricultural fair	Oripää	Lions Club Oripää	5.-8.7.2023
Field day about CE	Kokemäki	MTK	9.10.2023
Workshop on biobased side and waste streams	Tampere	TREASoURcE	31.10.2023
Agricultural Science Days, poster	Helsinki	Finnish Society of Agricultural Science	10.-11.1.2024
Wastewater treatment plant event	Mänttä-Vilppula	TREASoURcE	19.3.2024
Security of supply by promoting the circular economy -lecture	Tampere	TREASoURcE	18.4.2024
Farmari -agricultural fair	Seinäjoki	ProAgria	4.-6.7.2024

Central Finland Circular Economy Fair	Jyväskylä	CECE (Center of Expertise for CE)	28.8.2024
Working group on recycled fertilizers	Online	FER-PLAY project	4.9.2024
Webinar: Nutrient recycling in Baltic Sea Region	Online	EUSBSR	23.9.2024
Food waste working group meeting	Online	DG SANTE & Copa-Cogeca	14.10.2024
Agricultural Machine Fair	Helsinki	Helsinki Fair Centre	17.- 19.10.2024
Webinar: Bio & CE, Valorising secondary raw materials	Online	Estonian Chamber of Agriculture and Commerce	18.12.2024
Bioeconomy group meeting	Online	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry in Finland	17.1.2025
Replication seminar, Estonia	Online	TREASoURcE	4.2.2025
Waste and Circular Economy Cooperation Group	Hybrid (Helsinki)	Ministry of the Environment	26.2.2025
Circular bioeconomy – valorisation of forest by-products -workshop	Kouvola	The EU CAP Network	26.3.2025

To boost the marketing coverage of the KiertoaSuomesta.fi platform, social media accounts were created to Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn during fall 2023 and have been used since then. Altogether the accounts have 685 followers (LinkedIn 196, Instagram 451, and Facebook 38).

The social media accounts were taken into active use in December 2023, with the launch of the first CE Christmas Calendar for agriculture. It featured 22 innovative farmers showcasing their farms and circular practices. Beyond promoting farms and circularity in agriculture, the calendar aimed to raise awareness among farmers. Positive feedback led to its return in 2024 with a new theme: CE tips. Each day showcased practical ways to enhance farm circularity, with farmers sharing their initiatives. Figure 11 presents screenshots of both calendars.

Both Christmas calendars received very good feedback from the innovative way to promote CE in agriculture. They also achieved good visibility, with the posts from the calendar in 2024, for example, over 22 000 views were reached. Both social media calendars were prepared in collaboration with MTK-Satakunta's project "Muutosvoimaa tulevaan".

Figure 11. CE Christmas calendars 2023 (left) and 2024 were published on the marketplace's social media accounts.

Several articles about the KiertoaSuomesta.fi marketplace have been published in various media outlets. Maaseudun Tulevaisuus, the second most-read newspaper in Finland, has featured 3 articles during the TREASoURcE project. Additionally, a comprehensive article was published in Poultry magazine (Siipikarja), and in 2025, Positio magazine also published an online article highlighting the platform (Positio, 2025), among many other online texts published on the KiertoaSuomesta.fi platform itself and on [MTK's website](#) (MTK, 2025).

KiertoaSuomesta.fi
edistää sivuvirtojen markkinoita

Siipikarjilla voi löytää käyttäen ylimääräiseksi kananlannalle uudella kauppapaikalla. Verkkopalvelu auttaa ohjaamaan muitakin maataloudessa syntyviä sivuvirtoja hyötykäyttöön mualla.

Nora Berglund
Projektipäällikkö
MTK

KiertoaSuomesta.fi on uudelleen digitalisoitu markkinapaikka, joka tarjoaa mahdollisuuden biopohjaisten sivuvirtojen, kuten kananlannan, ottamiseen ja myymiseen. Palvelu yhdistää maan- ja metsätalouden sekä teollisuuden toimijat, jotka tuottavat tai hyödyntävät sivuvirtoja. Kanaalasta on arvokas resurssi, ja alustan avulla voi tehokkaasti markkinoida lantaa muille viljelijöille lannoituskäyttöön tai esimerkiksi teollisuuden hyödyntämiseksi. KiertoaSuomesta.fi tarjoaa vaivattoman tavan löytää sivuvirtoja ostajia.

Markkinapaikan keskeisenä tavoitteena on luoda maantilalle uudenlaisia liiketoimintamahdollisuuksia ja edistää yhteistyötä eri toimijoiden välillä. Samalla tuetaan alueellisia ravinne- ja materiaalikiertoja sekä pidetään lannoitusresurssit käytössä mahdollisimman pitkään.

Sivulla löytyy myös tietopaketti, jossa on materiaalia sivuvirtojen hyödyntämisestä sekä kiertotalouden edistämisestä.

"Juuri nyt, kun ryhtymään otuksia aletaan suunnitella, on erittäin tärkeää varmistaa, että lannan kiertyä ja tarjota kohtavat optimaalisesti. Monella tilalla on tarvetta lannalle, kun taas toisilla voi olla ylijääntä", summaa sivustolta kehittäjä MTK:n projektipäällikkö Nora Berglund.

"Kauppapaikalla toimijat voivat helposti löytää toisensa ja solmia kauppaa. Tavoitteen on edistää markkinoita alhustalouden sivuvirtoille ja samalla tuoda tilalle taloudellista hyötyä kiertotaloudesta."

Markkinapaikka keskittyy erityisesti biopohjaisiin sivuvirtoihin, kuten lantaa, oiketta, nurmikasvillisin, ylijääntärehun tai biookasainan mädätysjätteen.

Kiertotalous on paljon muutakin kuin vain kierrätystä. Sen päättävöitteenä on pitää resurssit käytössä mahdollisimman pitkään. Tämä voi olla esimerkiksi ryokasien ja laitteiden käyttöön pidentämistä, koneiden yhteiskäyttöä tai energianvarausuuden edistämistä.

Maataloudessa kiertotalous voi tarkoittaa myös eri toimijoiden, joilla pyritään parantamaan maan laatuolosuhteita, tehostamaan ravinteiden pidentymistä ja hallitsemaan vesiä. Lannan hyödyntämisen lisäksi tilat voi olla esimerkiksi viljelykieron monipuolista, alus- ja keräjäkasvien käyttöä, palkokasvien viljelyä tai maan muokkausten vähentämistä.

Nämä kaikki tukevat maaperän kaavunantaa ja voivat vähentää lannoituksen tarvetta. Kiertotalous on myös biokaasun tuotannon edistäminen esimerkiksi syyteiden, mädättämisen tai kaunun kautta. Tämä edistää energia- ja ravinnonvarausuutta ja parantaa huoltovarausuutta.

Biokaasuprojektin myötä biokaasuvirtoja syntyy ravinteiltaan mädätysjätteenä poltella. Samalla biokaasu vähentää riippuvuutta fossiilista polttoaineesta ja pienentää kokonaispäästöjä.

KOLMEN KEHITYSKOHTTEEN EU-HANKE

KIERTOASUOMESTA.FI kauppapaikka on toteutettu osana TREASoURcE -hanketta (2022-2026, Horizon Europe) -hanketta. Sen tavoitteena on edistää kiertotaloutta alueellisten pilottien avulla. Projektin keskeisiä kohteita ovat esimerkiksi: 1) hyödyntämisen mahdollistaminen sivu- ja jätevirtojen, etenkin maan- ja metsätaloudesta.

Hankkeen osallistuu 16 organisaatiota pääasiain Pohjois-Euroopasta. MTK on projektissa mukana erityisesti vahvistamassa kiertotaloutta maan- ja metsätaloudesta.

Markkinapaikalla voi myös löytää biokaasufabrikalle sopivia syyteitä tai tarjota mädätysjätettä viljelijöille, kavussa tuken uut biokaasulain pöytäkirja.

Kiertotalous.fi auttaa edistämään kansallista tehostusta hyödyntämisestä, mikä tukee kestävää maataloutta ja kiertotaloutta.

KiertoaSuomesta.fi on maatalouden kiertotalouden markkinoita. KiertoaSuomesta.fi on maatalouden kiertotalouden markkinoita. KiertoaSuomesta.fi on maatalouden kiertotalouden markkinoita.

Mutta palveluun voi myös tarjota esimerkiksi urakointipalveluita, kuten lannan kierrätystä. Rakentamisen tapahtuu sähköpostin ja y-tunnuksen avulla, palvelu on toistuvasti saatavilla yritykille. Kirjautuminen kirjautuminen voi luoda yrityksi- tai ostajatoimikunta, nähdä ilmoitusten tarkat tiedot, kuten osoitteen ja ilmoittajan yhteystiedot. Kanaalirykkyä ostajan ja myyjien välillä tapahtuu alustan välillä.

Myös talous kiittää kiertotaloutta

Ravinteiden kiertyminen ei ole sinänsä ympäristöystävällistä, vaan se tarjoaa myös taloudellisia mahdollisuuksia tiloille, samalla vähentämällä riippuvuutta mineraalilannoituksesta.

Siipikarjan lanta on erinomainen fosforin lähde, ja sen tehokas hyödyntäminen on tärkeä ravinnokierron kannalta. Fosforin kiertyminen onkin keskeinen maatalouden kiertotalouden Suomessa, mistä lantafosfori on keskittynyt kotimaisiin alueille. Lanta on ravinteikas raaka-aine ja erityisen tärkeä resurssi huoltovarausuuden ja ravinnonvarausuuden kannalta.

Suomessa viljelytuotantokäytökset ovat osittainon maaperän fosforipitoisuus laskeutunut viime vuosikymmeninä. Tämä on ollut hyvä kehitys, sillä liian korkeat fosforitasot voivat laata fosforin huoltovarausuutta väestön, mikä aiheuttaa rehevöitymistä. Toisaalta alhaiset fosforitasot voivat heikentää satoa, mikä kasvot eivät saa riittävästi fosforia.

Fosforinlannoitus on yksi tärkeistä työkaluista lannoitus kaavien tarkoituksen mukaan ja edistää ravinteiden pidentymistä, josta fosfori pysyy peltoissa, eikä leuureta vesistöihin.

Markkinapaikalla voi myös löytää biokaasufabrikalle sopivia syyteitä tai tarjota mädätysjätettä viljelijöille, kavussa tuken uut biokaasulain pöytäkirja.

14 HUOMIO SIIPIKARJA 1/2024

15 HUOMIO SIIPIKARJA 1/2024

Figure 12. Written article in Siipikarja (Poultry) - expert magazine.

An example of the produced texts is the article in the Poultry magazine, which highlights how poultry farms can find users for surplus chicken manure through the KiertoaSuomesta.fi marketplace (Figure

12). The article emphasizes the benefits of utilizing agricultural side streams, promoting regional nutrient and material cycles, and supporting the circular economy. It also provides practical information on how the marketplace facilitates the trading of side streams and encourages collaboration among various stakeholders.

The articles written have brought significant visibility to the platform, resulting in increased user traffic on the marketplace. Notably, one article by Maaseudun Tulevaisuus, which emphasized the demand for manure, led to several new listings being published on the site. Press releases have been offered to increase the marketing coverage of the platform.

A marketing video was also created to introduce agricultural and forestry side streams and their potential applications, such as organic soil improvers or use in the cosmetics industry. The video featured a farmer who extensively utilizes various biobased side streams from agriculture and the food industry for fertilization and soil improvement. The farmer shared insights into his advanced circular economy practices and encouraged others to explore opportunities to advance the sector. Additionally, a representative from a natural cosmetics company described how they aim to incorporate domestic biobased raw materials into their production. EcoFellows is the official commissioner of the video. A campaign for the video has been planned and will be launched in March 2025. The video was filmed in Finnish, but English subtitles were produced to the videos.

The video was published on [marketplace's Youtube channel](#) (KiertoaSuomesta, 2025).

Figure 13. Video about biobased side streams published in February 2025.

The number of active users on KiertoaSuomesta.fi has been steadily increasing, reflecting a growing interest in circular solutions within agriculture. By the end of February 2025, there were 27 listings on the marketplace, with the majority selling manure. In addition, listings included grass biomass, surplus feed, and a few individual posts offering biogas plant digestate and forestry side streams. This

development indicates that while manure remains the primary material being circulated, there is also interest in trading other biobased side streams. The increasing user activity suggests that awareness of the platform is expanding, and its role as a facilitator for side stream exchange is strengthening.

3.1.3 Future of the marketplace

Planning of the continuation of the KiertoaSuomesta.fi marketplace after the TREASoURcE project has been carried out since the beginning of the project. The platform's funding has been secured through the project's Horizon Europe funding until the project ends on May 31, 2026. However, at the time of the D5.4 submission in March 2025, the platform's funding after the project finishes is yet to be secured. This has been a key focus of the project and will become increasingly critical during the latter third of the project to ensure the future of the platform.

The MTK project team participated in the Pathways Incubator early-stage entrepreneurship programme organized by the University of Helsinki (2.2.-27.3.2024) to develop the marketplace, to market it and to get support for the possible incorporation of the marketplace in the future. The programme helped to identify opportunities and examples of different business opportunities for the marketplace as the aim is for the platform to be profitable by itself. The marketplace will have monthly maintenance expenses which include the regular maintenance, updates and support for the platform users. The marketing of the site is another expense that depends heavily on the actions taken.

The most potential revenue models for the marketplace:

- Advertisement: Income from third-party advertisements on the website.
- Transaction fees: Revenue generation through successful transactions.
 - Would require the trade to happen on the site – which currently is done off-site.
- Registration fees: User fee for registration and full access to the service.
- Subscription models: Packages for premium features and enhanced visibility on the platform.
- Licences: Offering separate user profile for commercial entities.
- Project funding: An interim option to ensure funding of the platform could be a project.

All the long-term income models for the platform would require reaching the critical mass of users in order for them to be possible. User fees, subscription models and advertisements will only bring significant value, if there is big enough group of users registering or audience for the ads. At the time of the deliverable reporting the user engagement has not been effective enough to put into practice the considered business models.

Discussions have been held with several important stakeholders for collaboration purposes and to examine possibilities for future funding of the marketplace. These include meetings with representatives of the funding bodies, the Finnish Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry and the Centres for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment, for instance. Meetings have also been arranged with the existing online marketplaces in Finland, Materiaalitori & Sivuvirtapörssi, and with projects aiming to build up new online marketplaces, such as DigiBiogasHubs project developing a

marketplace for biogas focusing on Ostrobothnia, Finland, and RuokoLog project aiming to create or co-develop a marketplace for Baltic reed.

3.2 Replication of marketplace in Estonia

Tallinn and Tartu conducted in spring 2023 a survey among wide range of stakeholders (agricultural sector, public sector, businesses) to find out an interest and a need for digital platform for biobased waste and side streams. Questionnaire was sent to 318 recipients. Altogether 5 responses were received. The low response rate is due to the lack of farmers in both municipalities and the government's ADDVAL-BIOEC project, which focused on added value and efficient use of raw materials in the bio-economy. Because of the large survey conducted by the government, the operators were not interested in answering a new one of the same type. The study results of ADDVAL-BIOEC are public and will be used in the project. A workshop with Tallinn's stakeholders on bio-based waste streams was conducted on March 24th, 2023, in the framework of task 6.1., to record concerns and ideas for future cooperation.

On February 4, 2025, an online replication seminar was organized in cooperation with Estonian project partners (Tallinn, TalTech, Tartu) to introduce the outcomes of the TREASoURcE project and assess the feasibility of implementing its solutions in Estonia. The seminar gathered 59 participants, 90% of whom were representatives from local municipalities. One of the key topics presented was the concept of a digital marketplace for biowaste and biobased side-streams, based on the Finnish KiertoaSuomesta.fi model. Dedicated discussion time was used to gather feedback on the feasibility of localizing this type of platform.

Discussions highlighted that while a digital platform could be useful for smaller biowaste streams, larger streams are already tied to long-term contracts and effectively utilized. A particularly underexplored biowaste stream is that generated in private second homes, which suggests seasonal fluctuations in biowaste production. While the platform is likely to be used primarily by businesses, public data on available waste streams could help small-scale entrepreneurs identify underutilized resources in specific municipalities and create new business opportunities. Additionally, participants noted that such a platform could serve as a matchmaking tool to connect producers and users, facilitating collaboration and enabling cost-sharing for transportation. However, previous experience in Estonia with a similar platform (Materjalivoog OÜ, 2025) has shown low adoption, raising concerns about the platform's long-term viability. A key unresolved issue is governance—there is no clear stakeholder willing to manage the platform, and the state has expressed no interest in taking on this role. Furthermore, the platform alone would not provide a complete overview of biowaste streams at the national level. However, participants discussed the potential for adapting the platform for more localized use, such as within an industrial park where businesses have established relationships and are more inclined to share data. Meanwhile, a state-led study is underway to determine how to achieve a comprehensive overview of waste streams in Estonia.

3.2.1 The Qualitative Study: Evaluating the Transferability Potential in Estonia

3.2.1.1 Introduction

In the framework of the Task 6.2, TalTech conducted a series of semi-structured individual and focus group interviews (the study henceforth) to evaluate the replicability/transferability potential of the digital marketplace in Estonia. The value proposition canvas was used as a guiding concept to conduct the interviews and focus groups. It helps to map the developer's perspective regarding the aim of the service that they provide, its benefits and expectations on the one hand, and the needs and viewpoint of the potential clients, on the other hand. The following stakeholder categories were approached during the study:

- Owner/developer of the service
- Professional associations/unions
- Public sector
- Agricultural enterprises
- Waste valorisation companies

In total 3 individual interviews and 2 focus group interviews were conducted during autumn 2024 until winter 2025. Interviews lasted between 60-90 minutes and were recorded and transcribed. Following list provides detailed information:

- Focus Group 1 – 5.12.2025 (2 participants represented following organisations: the Estonian Ministry of Agriculture, the Biogas Association in Estonia)
- Focus Group 2 – 9.12.2025 (6 participants represented following organisations: the Estonian Ministry of Climate, the Environmental Agency, Estonian Chamber of Commerce and Agriculture, Tallinn Circular Economy Center, Estonian Farmers' Union)
- Interview A – 8.11.2025 (participant: MTK)
- Interview B – 4.02.2025 (participant: representative of the biogas plant)
- Interview C – 12.02.2025 (participant: an intermediary between buyers and sellers of waste in Estonia)

3.2.1.2 Methodology

As mentioned above, the study is based on a value proposition analysis and structured in two stages. On the one hand, the service provider presents its service, together with its benefits and the solutions to the problems identified during its development. In the same way, the service provider defines its vision, i.e. the potential needs, problems and motivation (will) of the target market. Once these nuances have been identified, the second step is to examine their overlap with consumer or related target market aspects to identify the "jobs-to-be-done". By considering the views of both parties (service and

target market), the analysis can identify both the benefits of the service and the barriers to its implementation in the existing system.

Figure 14. Value proposition. Methodology for the survey and interviews.

In order to assess all possible aspects of the overlap between the digital market for biobased side and waste streams and the needs of the target market, a first interview with a potential service provider was carried out, following the structure of the value proposition analysis (Figure 14 & Figure 15). Subsequently, the target market was interviewed through eight different perspectives: waste recovery, regulations and legislation, new business models, expectations of the digital market platform, cross-supply chain collaboration, awareness, stakeholder pressure and readiness, and future vision. To this end, key questions for semi-structured interviews were drafted, considering the need of the target audience to pick up the most and least important topics.

From the public sector's perspective, the focus is consistently directed towards biobased side and waste streams. At the level of various ministries, waste streams generated in agriculture are being addressed, bioeconomy models have been developed, and circular bioeconomy roadmaps have been created. Solutions are also being worked on, how to valorise biodegradable waste and how to reduce the generation of waste as residues, as well as waste reform (which is mainly aimed at municipal waste). In addition to biodegradable waste, the issues of agricultural plastics and batteries are also closely related.

The needs of the target group through the eyes of the service creator

TARGET GROUPS: farms and professional associations; public authorities and local authorities; valuers			
Main Job-to-be-Done			
Target market needs	Client problems	"Jobs-to-be-done"	Client wants
<p>COMPANIES AND ASSOCIATIONS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - utilise resources sustainably more efficient waste disposal - cheaper access to secondary raw materials. 	<p>COMPANIES AND ASSOCIATIONS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - getting rid of waste is difficult 		<p>COMPANIES AND ASSOCIATIONS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - easier and faster ways to get rid of waste. - Greater confidence by not being tied to national statistics.
<p>VALORIZING COMPANIES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - more efficient recycling planning - possibility to use local bio-based secondary raw materials. 	<p>VALORIZING COMPANIES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lack of overview of potential suppliers - lack of awareness in product innovation in waste recycling 		<p>VALORIZING COMPANIES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - increase in recycling volumes - more opportunities for product innovation
<p>PUBLIC SECTOR:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sale of waste by-products from owned land. - municipal waste management planning. - development of regional bio-economy models - development of targeted waste recycling activities. 	<p>PUBLIC SECTOR:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Insufficient understanding of waste generation and side streams 		<p>PUBLIC SECTOR:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved insight into waste generation and waste streams

Figure 15. Customer profile. Methodology for the survey and interviews.

The professional associations that participated in the study are characterised by representing farmers and dealing with current problems in the field. For example, in addition to agricultural waste, additional attention is being paid to agricultural plastics and the development of biogas plants, including ensuring the security of supply of materials. According to data from 2022, there are 8 biomethane plants and 4 industrial biogas plants in Estonia (Eesti Biogaasi Assotsiatsioon, 2022). It is known that 5 plants have been submitted for the construction of additional biogas plants within the framework of the measures.

The valorising companies are mostly farmers who largely use the resulting residues based on established skills and knowledge, but also biogas plant holders. This can also be used to describe the sector more generally - agricultural waste is not the biggest problem in the field of waste, since the vast majority of the volume ends up back on the field, so to speak. However, this study also considers the circular economy centre, which operates all waste stations in Tallinn, where, in addition to other types of special waste (about 40 types), plastic and biodegradable garden waste are also handled.

3.2.1.3 "Jobs-to-be-done" in local areas and in EU level

To replicate the digital marketplace in Estonia, the study identified the "jobs-to-be-done" for the developer of the platform based on the value proposition framework. The study was conducted through in-depth interviews with various public authorities and professional associations, as well as with representatives of a biogas plant and an agricultural residue broker. In addition to the developer's needs, the national 'jobs-to-be-done' that would enable the application of such digital markets in Estonia were also identified. An in-depth study was conducted in Estonia to explore the replication of the platform in Latvia, Lithuania, Poland and Northern Germany, based on the main findings. The interviews with representatives of other countries will be based on the assumption that they are EU Member States subject to the same directives on agricultural waste, and therefore the in-depth study carried out in Estonia will serve as a basis for other countries.

During the interviews, the developer-driven "jobs-to-be-done" digital market application was identified:

- Ensuring that the exchanged product has passed the necessary analyses is of particular importance, especially in the case of agricultural residues, where there is a higher risk of transfer of biological hazards in the residue use area. For example, it is important to carry out analyses on silage if it is to be used to feed dairy cattle, so as to avoid an increase in the incidence of miscarriages. Additionally, the utilisation of sludge for refining is constrained by its chemical compounds.
- The platform should be prepared to establish cross-connectivity with national systems to ensure environmental authorisation requirements and sales and purchase rights are met. As environmental permits applied for are registered in a separate database in Estonia, it is envisaged that it would be both possible and necessary to link the same database to the sales platform. The national data system will facilitate the automatic identification of permits held by both the seller and the buyer, enabling the platform to determine the validity of their placement of waste for sale. In the absence of the relevant permits, the system will automatically block transactions, and, conversely, will allow transactions to proceed if the permits are deemed to be invalid.
- The focus is directed towards smaller and less volatile waste flows, with the understanding that the large and main waste streams (manure, silo, etc.) are well-established, and regional biogas plants are involved in these streams. This is primarily due to the high investment required to build a biogas plant. Smaller streams are primarily concerned with regions where there are no biogas plants in geographically defined proximity, or waste types that are less generated and of unstable volumes. Consequently, developers may face the challenge of managing a reduced volume of waste flows, which can also result in a more limited user base for the platform. This prompts the question of how to ensure the sustainable development of the platform, particularly from a financial perspective.

- The identification of solutions to facilitate the utilisation of the sales platform, particularly for waste sellers, is paramount. Practitioners have noted the extensive use of numerous platforms, which necessitates a substantial time investment. Furthermore, the uploading of images and relevant information may not be feasible or a priority for all potential users, highlighting the importance of integrating automated solutions into workflows to reflect relevant information on the platforms as far as possible, particularly for the purchaser.
- It is crucial to ensure that comprehensive information is provided on the waste being sold, as practitioners have noted that a general description can act as a barrier to transactions and potentially result in the purchase of substandard or unusable waste. This necessitates ensuring direct contact between the buyer and the seller of the waste.
- Furthermore, it is essential to ensure that the market price of the waste is competitive. The sale of residues is perceived as a means of generating additional income; however, as farmers do not prioritise the sale of residues, they might lack awareness of their actual monetary value. Furthermore, a considerable proportion of waste is seasonal in nature, resulting in significant fluctuations in selling prices from year to year. Consequently, the platform must ensure a minimum market price that is aligned with the quality and seasonality of the waste being sold. This is necessary to ensure that farmers also derive benefit from the sale of residues, thereby encouraging the increased valorisation of agricultural waste.
- The sales platform should be prepared to function as an information centre, providing clear and accessible information on recycling opportunities, legislation, regulations, and support measures to both buyers and sellers. Additionally, there is a necessity to identify methods of integrating the platform with R&D institutions to enhance awareness and promote product innovation in the field of waste recycling.
- Furthermore, the platform should be expanded to encompass multiple sectors. For instance, a biogas plant or a farmer is not only dependent on agricultural residues, but also on residues from the food and drink industry. Conversely, agricultural residues are not only used by farms. For instance, the horticultural sector has expressed interest in fertilisers, given the transition in climate policy towards a substantial reduction in peat extraction, which will consequently diminish the availability of peat substrate. Other sectors, such as the chemical industry and those that irrigate agricultural residues, have also expressed interest in fertilisers.

The interviews also identified broader issues that need to be addressed at EU and national level.

- Firstly, EU Member States appear to need to modernise and clarify the terms 'waste', 'residues' and 'by-products', and to adjust the system of waste codes, particularly regarding sector-specific issues. For instance, digestate from biogas production is classified as a residue from a national perspective, yet as a by-product from the perspective of the biogas producer, who inherently generates it during the production process. However, for the purpose of directing

digestate to farmers for utilisation as a soil amendment, it is imperative for them to obtain an environmental permit authorising the use of digestate as a residue. Analogous scenarios with different types of waste exist in other sectors, underscoring the necessity to align definitions to align with EU climate policy objectives.

- At the national level, it is imperative to identify a solution that simplifies the application process for waste permits. For instance, a biogas plant has applied for environmental permits for those crucial waste streams utilised in the production process. However, this precludes the possibility of promptly incorporating production waste from the food industry (e.g. yoghurt waste) or low-volume, unstable waste streams (e.g. potatoes) from farmers. The process of obtaining an environmental permit is typically protracted (typically spanning approximately one year) and entails substantial financial costs. Concurrently, it is acknowledged that rarely used residues may not be utilised without a permit, and their energy value and quality suitability will be diminished if they are stored.
- The establishment of industrial symbiosis parks in proximity to biogas facilities throughout the country is recommended. These parks should incorporate a pyrolysis plant, facilitating the refinement of woody biomass (e.g. stumps). Additionally, enterprises capable of sharing locally generated energy, materials and water should be included.

The primary conclusion is that the digital market developer should consider strategies to ensure a substantial user base, as well as identify potential leaders and financiers for platform development. In order to mitigate risks, it would be worthwhile to focus on specific and unstable agricultural residues, to extend the use of the platform across different industrial sectors and to ensure a competitive price for the waste streams. From the seller's point of view, it is important to ensure the ease of use of the platform and, from the buyer's point of view, a detailed overview of the residues to be sold. It is also imperative to ensure that the entire process of buying and selling complies with legislation and regulations.

The suggestions, primarily aimed at the developer, will be further developed in the next phase of the study, when relevant actors in other target countries will be interviewed. The analysis of interview data continues in Task 6.2. The full analysis will be available in the Replication Handbook (TRESoURcE, 2025b).

3.3 Replication of marketplace in Norway

There are different platforms for selling and buying bio-based side and waste streams in Norway, the dominant player is Finn.no, a general digital second-hand marketplace with a large sub-site on agricultural items and waste streams. There are some start-ups that try to focus more in the b2b market overall. There are several marketplaces focusing on either a specific bio-based resource (like wood) or a variety of bio-based waste streams in agriculture. In addition to the digital marketplaces, there are also several actively used Facebook sub-groups and sites that primarily serve the local/regional market in the trade of biobased side and waste streams.

A list of examples of current marketplaces for biobased resources in Norway:

- [Finn.no](#) Dominant player, covers almost any product/service (Schibsted ASA, n.d.)
- [Vednett.no](#) Focus on ads for wood logs, national site, geographical division by county (Vednett, n.d.)
- [Ressursbank](#) - Resource streams platform (Norwegian Centre of Circular Economy, n.d.)
- [Markedsplassen](#) - Various side streams, such as bio char, eggshells, wood chips (Resourcer, n.d.).

The site for selling/buying of wood logs has a very user-friendly layout and functionality, which might be useful to investigate for partners looking to develop existing market sites.

The Finnish marketplace has been presented to representatives from the Farmers union Norway and been discussed with the steering committee of the partnership Climate-smart Agriculture. These thorough discussions indicated that there is currently no urgent need to implement a similar digital tool in Norway. Consequently, there are no immediate plans to replicate KiertoaSuomesta.fi digital marketplace.

However, the further development and dissemination of the digital rural-urban symbiosis tool (to be created in T5.3 “Understanding rural-urban symbiosis – building circular areas”) could offer significant benefits and serve as a valuable alternative to a marketplace. This tool will provide a detailed guideline for achieving rural-urban collaboration and integrate the mapping tool already developed by Fredrikstad Municipality, which is presented in chapter 2.2.3.3. Fredrikstad Municipality will therefore further develop and promote the digital rural-urban symbiosis tool, fostering new business.

3.4 Public procurement promoting the use of biobased resources

Procurement can be an effective tool in advancing circular bioeconomy, and in supporting the use of biobased side and waste streams. In collaboration with WP2, as part of task 2.2.3 “CE-smart procurers,” various strategies have been explored to empower municipalities in promoting these resources through procurement. By prioritizing biogas and recycled fertilizers, procurement can drive significant environmental benefits, including emission reductions, decreased dependence on raw materials, nutrients, and energy, as well as fostering a shift towards renewable energy sources. In addition to

environmental benefits, it also supports local economies, enhances long-term self-sufficiency, increases the security of supply through decentralized energy production, and the utilization of local biomasses.

Public procurement can further support the circular bioeconomy by prioritizing biogas as a transportation fuel. Requiring biogas-powered vehicles in public transport contracts or introducing incentives such as tax benefits, company car benefits, and reduced parking fees can encourage wider use of biogas. Furthermore, integrating biogas infrastructure, such as biogas filling stations, into urban planning supports the operational environment for biogas.

One key aspect in procurement for biobased resources is to have them noted in the local, regional or national strategies or/and in the strategies of private companies. Strategies that include biogas as a core component are essential to ensure a sustainable operational environment for biogas. Investments in biogas plants and support for projects exploring biomass gasification potential are essential to unlocking the value of agricultural side streams and other biodegradable wastes. By (re)directing these waste streams to biogas plants and supporting research into sustainable biowaste solutions, public procurement can strengthen circular practices. Collaborating with publicly owned heating and electricity companies, as well as incentivizing stakeholders through financial support and development participation, can bolster biogas adoption and the local CE ecosystem.

Based on the Task 2.2.3 “CE-smart procurers” a procurement recipe booklet will be created, which will be published in spring 2026. The booklet will include guidelines, criteria and instructions for procurement and market dialogue also for biobased side and waste streams, biogas and composting, for example.

3.4.1. Municipalities’ interests towards biogas and recycled fertilizers

As part of the project, a master’s thesis in a university of applied sciences was initiated to gather insights into municipalities’ and cities’ current practices and motivations regarding the use of biogas and recycled fertilizers, with a particular focus on how procurement could support these goals. A questionnaire was sent to 57 municipalities in July 2024, with two follow-up rounds in autumn to encourage responses. Despite these efforts, only nine responses were received, revealing challenges in engaging municipalities on these topics.

The survey results revealed key insights. For biogas, several municipalities indicated that improved availability, lower overall costs, and better profitability would be valuable drivers. However, financial constraints were commonly cited as a barrier to investments, such as acquiring gas-powered vehicles. Some respondents also mentioned that CO₂ accounting methods did not demonstrate reductions from biogas use in certain cases, which further influenced their decisions. Regarding recycled fertilizers, many municipalities mentioned having considered them but lacked a clear understanding of the current market situation. Factors that could encourage their use include competitive market prices,

guaranteed purity of products, and improved municipal finances. Decisions at the administrative level were also identified as critical drivers for adopting these solutions.

To complement the limited survey data, interviews will be conducted in spring 2025 to gather more detailed and representative information. Despite the challenges, the thesis is on track for completion by summer 2025.

3.4.2. Case examples of municipalities promoting biogas

City of Nokia & Verte - Verte Oy is a platform company owned by the city of Nokia in Finland that focuses on the development of ECO3 area. In the ECO3 area, bio- and circular economy businesses and innovations are developed on an industrial scale. ECO3 is a nationally significant competence centre, which also runs various demonstrations and pilots. Among other things, the area is home to a biogas plant operated by Pirkanmaan Jätehuolto Oy, which started to operate in 2023. The methane produced by the biogas plant is planned to be equivalent to around 2.5 million litres of liquid transport fuels per year.

In 2018, the City of Nokia purchased environmentally friendly gas cars. The city purchased 26 passenger cars and one truck to replace its obsolete fleet. The procurement of the gas vehicles was based on the City of Nokia's strategy, which includes the introduction of sustainable and ecological solutions as one of its objectives. It is also in line with the development of the ECO3 area.

Municipality of Vieremä - The Finnish municipality of Vieremä serves as a pioneering example of how municipalities can promote and advance biogas in their regions. Vieremä has implemented an open raw gas transmission network, enabling local agricultural producers to supply biogas either as raw gas through pipelines or as container-transported gas suitable for vehicles. The municipality's energy and water company along with a local big forestry machine company, Ponsse, have committed to purchasing the gas under long-term contracts with guaranteed pricing. This ensures a secure market for producers and encouraging investment in farm-scale biogas plants.

The initiative utilizes local resources, such as underutilized grass biomasses, to produce biogas, and the gas is piped to a public filling station to support transport use. Vieremä has committed to transitioning its fleet to gas-powered vehicles, including field vans, a gas-powered tractor, a library vehicle, and official cars, with plans to incorporate gas-fueled options in future vehicle purchases and services. This approach not only creates a local market for biogas, fostering new business opportunities in gas production, maintenance, and feedstock supply, but also keeps energy expenditures within the region, boosting local vitality. By the municipality's decision to replace fossil fuels with biogas, Vieremä is setting a benchmark for sustainable energy and equitable access to cleaner transport solutions. (Kajanus, 2024)

City of Tallinn - In Estonia, biogas production began for the first time in 2010. Since then, several biogas plants have been built across the country. Due to the low demand for biogas in the transportation sector, most of the biogas produced was initially used for electricity and heat generation.

In 2019, the Tallinn Transport Department reorganized its bus fleet, aiming to contribute to cleaner city air and reduce the environmental footprint of urban transportation. Through a public procurement process, a significant number of gas-powered buses were purchased, and a second tender was announced. The main goal of the second procurement contract was to acquire compressed gas (natural gas and biomethane) for the gas buses and utility vehicles used by the Tallinn Transport Department. An additional goal of the contract was the construction of compressed gas refueling equipment (a total of two fueling stations) for selling gas to the procurer.

At the time of the tender announcement, there were no major biomethane suppliers in Estonia offering biomethane as a vehicle fuel. Therefore, the tender included a relatively lenient preference for acquiring biomethane. The technical description in the tender stated: “The procurer wishes to purchase biomethane as the first preference for the entire duration of the procurement contract. If the supplier is unable to sell biomethane, the procurer will purchase natural gas.”

The tender was won by Bioforce Infra OÜ, a company specializing in biomethane production. The contract was signed for eleven years. Bioforce Infra OÜ's core activity is the environmentally friendly processing of biomass, including animal by-products, as well as kitchen and catering biowaste, into biomethane. The company's integrated approach involves first sourcing suitable raw materials, then producing biogas, and finally upgrading it into biomethane. The nutrient-rich digestate produced as a by-product is returned to agriculture, serving as a prime example of successful circular economy implementation at the local level. Tallinn's CNG filling stations play a key role in reducing the environmental impact of the city's public transport system while supporting the community's commitment to achieving a cleaner and greener urban environment.

Today, the majority of Tallinn's city buses run on compressed gas. In total, 350 gas-powered buses operate on Tallinn's streets, and a state procurement is currently underway to acquire an additional 50 gas buses. At present, Bioforce Infra OÜ does not yet produce enough biomethane to meet the entire demand of Tallinn's bus network. However, biomethane production is increasing annually. According to forecasts, 80% of the compressed gas needs of Tallinn's gas buses will be covered by biomethane by 2025. Since 2019, Tallinn has held a significant role as a market leader in biomethane, accounting for 40% of Estonia's total biomethane consumption.

4. BIOGAS INCENTIVES – POLICY BRIEF

Policy framework can play a critical role in enabling the development of circular value chains, influencing how biobased side and waste streams are utilized (Vural Gursel et al., 2022). Clear and supportive policies can accelerate investments, enhance market predictability, and create incentives for industries to adopt circular practices. Within this project, regulatory analysis was conducted to identify barriers and opportunities in the legislative landscape. While the original task concluded with the preliminary policy recommendations, further work was undertaken to refine specific recommendations on Finnish biogas incentives, given their significant role in fostering the circular economy. Chapter 4 presents the outcomes of this effort, detailing the finalized policy brief and its dissemination to relevant stakeholders.

Significant groundwork was conducted under WP1 for task 1.3 “Legislative and regulatory framework” to analyse CE regulatory frameworks and to identify regulatory drivers and barriers related to the collection, treatment, and recycling of biobased side and waste streams. This included desk research and stakeholder engagement workshops, resulting in initial policy recommendations aimed at enhancing circular practices for the value chains. The EU instruments assessed included directives, strategies, action plans, and standards. By May 2024, when the task ended, a preliminary summary of policy recommendations was produced which is found from the report [D1.3 Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains](#) (TREASoURcE, 2024).

The policy recommendations for biobased side and waste streams were grouped into three themes:

- 1) **Complexity and low predictability of policy instruments**
- 2) **Sewage sludge utilization and wastewater treatment**
- 3) **Lack of incentives for biogas in Finland**

Building on this earlier work, further efforts were made to refine and finalize policy recommendations, focusing specifically on the third theme: Finnish biogas incentives. This theme was prioritized based on its potential impact and relevance to the project’s objectives. The recommendations were further developed into a concise policy brief format. This process included deeper analysis and collaboration with stakeholders to ensure the recommendations effectively address emerging challenges and opportunities in the biogas sector, which are topical for lobbying.

The finalized policy brief provides targeted insights to support the development and secure the continuation of biogas incentives and contribute to advancing CE practices in Finland. The policy brief, published in Finnish, is available in Annex 3, with the English translation provided below. The policy brief was published in January 2025 as a media release, with the aim of wide distribution. Additionally, the brief was sent directly to key government officials at the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment, the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, and the Ministry of Transport and Communications - central actors in advancing the biogas sector in Finland. It was also disseminated through the websites and social media channels of KiertoaSuomesta.fi, MTK, and the TREASoURcE project. Furthermore,

the policy brief was presented in a roundtable discussion organized by eight sectoral associations in Finland on March 19, 2025, which was streamed for all interested parties.

4.1. Policy brief: The continuation of biogas incentives must be ensured

Biogas enables the conversion of biobased side streams and waste into renewable energy and recycled nutrients. The production of biogas increases the security of supply in our society in terms of energy and fertilizers, supports the favourable development of the local economy, and at the same time helps Finland achieve its carbon neutrality goals by reducing emissions. The development of the biogas sector in Finland has been accelerated in recent years by the increased use of liquefied biogas as fuel for heavy transport. In 2022, 0.9 terawatt hours (TWh) of biogas were produced in Finland (Statistics Finland, 2024). However, the estimated techno-economic production potential is 10 TWh, of which up to 86% is based on agricultural inputs (Marttinen et al., 2015). The Biogas Vision published by industry organizations in August 2024 sets the goal of increasing production to four terawatt-hours by 2030 (Biokaasuvisio2030, 2024). The efficient and optimized utilization of agricultural side streams (manure, grass, straw) enables biogas production, which has significant economic, ecological, and social importance for our society.

There are several biogas plant projects of various sizes underway across the country – both large industrial investments and small-scale farm plants. These projects are hindered by profitability challenges related to biogas production and its position and future in the energy sector. The markets for renewable gases and recycled fertilizers are still developing, which increases the risk level of investments. The insufficiency of investment subsidies reduces the number of investments, and there is a need for various incentives to ensure the viability of the sector. Small-scale and early-stage biofuel production is more expensive than fossil fuels, and incentives are needed during the market development phase.

The support forms and mechanisms for the biogas sector need predictability, and political decisions have a significant impact on the development of the sector. Specific challenges have been caused by the reduction of support for biogas plants and changes in the fuel distribution obligation, such as lowering obligation levels, changes in the scope of the distribution obligation (synthetic fuels, electricity), and upcoming changes to penalty fees. In rural areas, the accessibility of the gas network causes regional inequality, highlighting the need to investigate logistics support. The national biogas program drafted in 2020 needs to be updated to ensure the continuity of support and the establishment of biogas in regulations.

Recommendations for Finnish decision-makers

1. Finland must update the national biogas program published by Prime Minister Marin's government in 2020 and ensure the continuation of the program.

2. The continuation of investment subsidies for biogas plants and recycling of nutrients must be ensured.
3. The additional obligation level of the fuel distribution obligation for transport fuels must be raised to increase the demand for biogas.
4. The purchase subsidy for gas-powered heavy-duty vehicles should continue to be granted to increase the demand for biogas. The subsidy should also be extended to the purchase of public transport and delivery vehicles.
5. The position of biogas in emission regulations for heavy transport and maritime transport must be established in favour of biogas.
6. The possibility of transport support for transporting biomethane to be injected into the natural gas network must be investigated.

Case study: Lack of funds for biogas investments in Finland

In Finland, the funding possibilities for biogas investments are limited. Farms and farm cooperatives can receive funding from the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. However, the budget is limited. For instance, municipalities and companies owned by municipalities, such as wastewater treatment plants, can receive funding for their biogas investments from the Ministry of the Environment if their project also considers nutrient recycling. However, this support is ending, and the last application opportunities are in 2024.

The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment will continue to grant subsidies also for biogas investments. However, the budget for energy subsidies has decreased from €100 million last year to €14 million in 2024 (Ministry of Employment and Economy, 2024). Business Finland has the funding authority. Funding has been decided to be granted only for value-added biogas plant investments, such as plants using new technologies. Additional EU RRF funding has been available until 2024 but is now coming to an end.

This policy brief has been produced as part of the TREASoURcE project Task 1.3 "Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains". It provides a basis for policy makers and stakeholders to develop effective policies to promote circular economy transition. This policy brief is based on a literature review and stakeholder consultation, to validate the findings. The project report D1.3 Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains addresses critical challenges and opportunities to promote the circular economy transition. The T1.3 was finished in May 2023, but the WP5 continued to develop the policy paper and published the paper in January 2025.

Partners: MTK, VTT, EcoFellows, CLIC Innovation & Business Tampere

The published policy brief in Finnish can be found from Annex 3.

5. REFERENCES

- Agency, E. (2025). *Environmental Agency*. Retrieved 2 28, 2025, from https://tableau.envir.ee/views/Avalikud_pringud_Jtmed/Omaavalitsusetasand?%3Aembed=y&%3Aiid=1&%3AisGuestRedirectFromVizportal=y
- AS, T. J. (2025). *Main page of Tallinna Jäätmete Taaskasutuskeskus AS*. Retrieved 2 14, 2025, from <https://tjt.ee/>
- Avfall Sverige. (2009). *Substrate handbook for biogas production*. Waste Sweden Report U2009:14.
- Biokaasuvisio2030. (2024). *Biokaasuvisio2030-julkilausuma*. Retrieved 9 2, 2024, from https://biokaasu2030.fi/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/Biokaasuvisio2030_14082024.pdf
- Data Norge. (n.d.). Felles datakatalog. Retrieved 2 21, 2025, from <https://data.norge.no/search-all>
- EC Directive 98. (2008). *Directive (EU) 98/2008 of the European Parliament on waste and repealing certain Directives*. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008L0098>
- Ecobio, E. (2025). *EKT main page*. Retrieved 2 14, 2025, from <https://ecobio.ee/>
- Eesti Biogaas OÜ. (2025). *Rohegaasijaam*. Retrieved 2 14, 2025, from <https://rohegaasijaam.ee/firmast/>
- Eesti Biogaasi Assotsiatsioon. (2022). *Biogaasijaamad Eestis*. Retrieved 2 14, 2025, from <https://www.eestibiogaas.ee/biogaasijaamad-eestis>
- Energiatalgud. (2022). Retrieved 2 14, 2025, from https://energiatalgud.ee/Biogaasi_energeetiline_ressurss
- European Commission. (2020). *A new Circular Economy Action Plan: For a cleaner and more competitive Europe*. EUR-Lex. Retrieved 1 15, 2025, from https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:9903b325-6388-11ea-b735-01aa75ed71a1.0017.02/DOC_1&format=PDF
- European Commission. (2020b). *Farm to Fork Strategy: For a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system*. EUR-Lex. Retrieved 1 15, 2025, from https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:ea0f9f73-9ab2-11ea-9d2d-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF
- European Commission; Joint Research Centre; Korosuo, A.; Borzacchiello, M.T.; Giuntoli, J.; Lasarte Lopez, J.; M`Barek, R.; Mubareka, S.B.; Camia, A. (2024). *Trends in the EU bioeconomy - update 2024*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. doi:10.2760/0141556
- HAMK. (n.d.). *Hygienized manure*. Retrieved from <https://www.hamk.fi/projektit/hygienisoitu-lanta/#perustiedot>
- Kajanus, M. (2024). *Hajautettu biokaasuntuotanto - Vieremän malli. Biokaasua Pirkanmaalle 3.0 - seminar presentation 29.10.2024*. Tampere, Finland. Retrieved 12 16, 2024, from <https://www.proagri.fi/uploads/Mikko-Kajanus-Viereman-kunta.pdf>

- Kersa, K. (2023). *Significant potential for biogas production in Estonia remains untapped*. Retrieved 2 14, 2025, from <https://news.err.ee/1608858038/significant-potential-for-biogas-production-in-estonia-remains-untapped>
- Keskkonnaagentuur. (2024). *Keskkonnaportaali*. Retrieved 2 14, 2025, from <https://keskkonnaportaali.ee/et/teemad/jaatmed/biojaatmed>
- Kiertoasuomesta. (2024). Retrieved 1 31, 2025, from <https://www.kiertoasuomesta.fi/>
- Kiertoasuomesta. (2025). Sivuvirrat ovat kysyttyjä raaka-aineita. Retrieved 2 28, 2025, from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r3cBI4QzyoY>
- Lange, L., Connor, K., Arason, S., Bundgård-Jørgensen, U., Canalis, A., Carrez, D., . . . Vieira, H. (2021). Developing a sustainable and circular bio-based economy in EU: by partnering across sectors, upscaling and using new knowledge faster, and for the benefit of climate, environment & biodiversity, and people & business. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*(8). doi:10.3389/fbioe.2020.619066
- Lohri, C., Diener, S., Zabaleta, I., Mertenat, A., & Zurbrügg, C. (2017). *Treatment technologies for urban solid biowaste to create value products: a review with a focus on low- and middle-income settings*. *Reviews in Environmental Science and Bio/Technology*.
- Luostarinen, S., Laakso, J., Tampio, E., Skyttä, A., & Lehtonen, E. (2023). *Ravinteiden kierrätyksen tilastointi ja seuranta*. Helsinki: Luonnonvara- ja biotalouden tutkimus 107/2023. Luonnonvarakeskus.
- Marttinen, S., Luostarinen, S., Winqvist, E., & Timonen, K. (2015). *Rural biogas: feasibility and role in Finnish energy system*. Helsinki: Cluster for Energy and Environment.
- Materjalivoog OÜ. (2025). *Materjalivoog*. Retrieved 12.02.2025, from <https://materjalivoog.ee/>
- Melbye, , A., Rørstad, P., & Killingland, M. (2014). *Bioenergi i Norge*. Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate`. Retrieved from https://publikasjoner.nve.no/rapport/2014/rapport2014_41.pdf
- Ministry of Employment and Economy. (2024). *Eligible projects and maximum amounts of aid*. Retrieved 10 15, 2024, from <https://tem.fi/tuettavat-hankeet>
- MTK. (2025). *TREASoURcE -hanke*. Retrieved 15 1, 2025, from <https://www.mtk.fi/treasure>
- Natural Resources Institute Finland. (2024). The Natural Resources data service. Suomi. Retrieved 12 16, 2024, from <https://www.luke.fi/fi/luonnonvaratieto/tiedetta-ja-tietoa/biomassaatlas/biomassaatlaksen-biomassat/pelto>
- Natural Resources Institute Finland. (2024b). OSF: Natural Resources Institute Finland, Structure of agricultural and horticultural enterprises. Retrieved 12 16, 2024, from https://statdb.luke.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/en/LUKE/LUKE__02%20Maatalous__02%20Rakenne__02%20Maatalous-%20ja%20puutarhayritysten%20rakenne/03_Maatalous_ja_puutarhayrit_lkm_tuotantos_ELY.px/table/tableViewLayout2/?rxid=786f0450-355f-4a91-af51-6898606f4e0f
- Ngo, T. (2023). *The operational environment of circular bio-based side and waste streams for biogas and nutrient recovery*. Tampere University.
- Norwegian Centre of Circular Economy. (n.d.). Resurssbank. Retrieved 9 1, 2025, from <https://ncce.no/no/ressursbank/>
- Norwegian Environment Agency. (n.d.). Norwegian effluents. Retrieved 2 21, 2025, from <https://www.norskeutslipp.no/en/Frontpage/?SectorID=90>

- Positio. (2025). Revolutionizing agricultural side streams – how location data can support side stream logistics? Location Innovation Hub. Retrieved 20 1, 2025, from <https://positio-magazine.eu/2025/01/revolutionizing-agricultural-side-streams-how-location-data-can-support-side-stream-logistics/>
- Ravinnekierto2030. (2020). Julkilausuma: Ravinteet ja hiili tehokkaaseen kiertoon vuoteen 2030. Suomi. Retrieved from <https://ravinnekierto2030.fi/>
- Resourcer. (n.d.). Markedsplassen. Retrieved 9 1, 2024, from <https://www.resourcer.bio/markedsplassen>
- Ruthon Services. (2025). Mobiiliseparointipalvelu. Retrieved 1 23, 2025, from <https://www.ruthonservices.fi/mobiiliseparointi/>
- Røsnes, E. (2021). *Matsvinn i jordbrukssektoren. Kartlegging for 2021*. Directorate of Agriculture, Norway. Retrieved from https://www.landbruksdirektoratet.no/nb/filarkiv/rapporter/Matsvinn%20i%20jordbrukssektoren,%20kartlegging%20for%202021%20Rapport%2012%202023.pdf/_attachment/inline/ffe69ebb-2b50-46ec-9cb4-f13f4769f3fe:a115954a121fc2b1c6d6ad2741cc0ced02596c3f/Matsvinn%20
- Schibsted ASA. (n.d.). *FINN.no*. Retrieved from <https://www.finn.no/>
- Statistics Finland. (2024). *Energy supply and consumption*. Retrieved 9 2, 2024, from <https://stat.fi/tilasto/ehk>
- Statistics Norway. (n.d.). StatBank Norway. Retrieved 2 21, 2025, from <https://www.ssb.no/en/statbank>
- Stensgård, A. E., & Callewaert, P. (2021). *Sector report on food waste in the food industry, public sector and households*. Norwegian institute for sustainability research (NORSUS). Retrieved from <https://norsus.no/en/publikasjon/sectorrapport-for-matbransjen-offentlig-sektor-og-husholdningsleddet/>
- Taraskin, A. (2023). *Biojäätméd*. Retrieved 2 14, 2025, from <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/3bdbf898902b47559a279dbb9d0a6655>
- TREASoURcE. (2023). *D1.1 Territories' CE activities and state-of-the-art of CE*. <https://treasource.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/TREASoURcE-D1.1-Territories-CE-activities-and-state-of-the-art.pdf>.
- TREASoURcE. (2023b). *D1.4 State-of-the-art analysis of technologies, circular business models and ecodesign practices for plastic waste, end-of-life electric vehicle batteries and bio-based side and waste streams*. <https://treasource.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/TREASoURcE-D1.4-State-of-the-art-analysis-of-technologies-circular-business-models-ecodesign-and-good-practices.pdf>.
- TREASoURcE. (2023c). *D5.1 Digital marketplace*. <https://treasource.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/TREASoURcE-D5.1-Digital-marketplace.pdf>.
- TREASoURcE. (2023d). *TREASoURcE network visualization*. Forum Virium Helsinki. Retrieved from <https://treasource.blob.core.windows.net/treasource/index.html>
- TREASoURcE. (2024). *D1.3 Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains*. <https://treasource.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/TREASoURcE-D1.3-Legislative-and-regulatory-framework-for-target-value-chains.pdf>.
- TREASoURcE. (2025). Retrieved 17 1, 2025, from <https://treasource.eu/>
- TREASoURcE. (2025b). Replication Handbook. Retrieved 2 18, 2025, from <https://handbook.treasource.eu/>

Vednett. (n.d.). Retrieved 9 1, 2024, from <https://www.vednett.no/>

Vural Gursel, I., Elbersen, B., Meesters, K. P., & van Leeuwen, M. (2022). Defining Circular Economy Principles for Biobased Products. *Sustainability*, 14(19).
doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912780>

Østfold County Governor. (2024). Data produksjonstilskudd. Retrieved 2 20, 2025, from <https://view.officeapps.live.com/op/view.aspx?src=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.statsforvalteren.no%2Fsiteassets%2Fm-vestfold-og-telemark%2Flandbruk-og-mat%2Fjordbruk%2Fpresentasjon-data-produksjonstilskudd-12062024.xlsx&wdOrigin=BROWSELINK>

ANNEX 1 – Biobased side and waste streams

Agricultural side and waste streams	Source
Animal waste	livestock farms
Bedding materials	livestock farms
Blood	slaughterhouse waste
Contaminated & leftover feed	livestock farms
Dredging waste	water bodies
Eggshells	poultry farms
Fawn	livestock farms
Feathers	poultry farms
Fish silage	aquaculture/fish farms
Fish waste	fish farms
Grass biomass	green manure leys, protection zones, nature management fields
Hatching hens	livestock farms
Horticultural residues	greenhouses, plant nurseries
Larvae residuals	leftovers from larvae production
Larvae waste	larvae production
Manure total	livestock farms
Seaweed / algae side and waste streams	Fisheries/fish farms
Slaughter waste: offal, intestines, bones	livestock & fish farms
Smolt	aquaculture/fish farms
Straw	leftovers from crop harvest
Trimming / orchard waste	horticulture
Unharvested crop	plant production farms
Unused vegetation: buffer strips, ditches, verges & wetlands	uncultivated land areas
Used growing media	horticulture
Vegetable and plant waste: -food waste not acknowledged by industry roots, tubers, stems, peelings -vegetables discarded due to shape and size -vegetable waste	plant production farms, unsuitable for retail
Waste seeds	plant production farms
Willows	land area
Wool/fleece - shorthaired, dyed, white	livestock farms

Forestry side and waste stream	Source
Ash	biorefineries, power plants
Bark	sawmills and plywood mills
Black liquor	chemical pulp mills
Energy wood, small-diameter trees	forest
Fiber sludge	paper, board & mechanical pulp mills
Forestry residuals in edge zones	forest
Logging residues, i.e. branches and treetops	forest
Sawdust	sawmills and plywood mills
Stumps	forest
Wood materials - reuse of agricultural buildings	barns, agricultural buildings
Woodchips	sawmills and plywood mills

Urban side and waste streams	Source
Food loss and food waste	food industry, tourism, catering, retail
Garden waste	households
Gutter oil	food industry, catering
Industrial waste	multiple
Municipal sludge	wastewater systems
Organic municipal solid waste; biowaste	households, restaurants, public sector
Unutilized vegetation	wastelands, road verges

ANNEX 2 – KiertoaSuomesta.fi marketing materials

3-page booklet presenting the digital marketplace, English version, 1/2

TREASOURcE-project

The TREASOURcE project, funded by the Horizon Europe programme (2022–2026), aims to enhance circular economy solutions through regional pilots. The project focuses on three value chains:

- unused plastic waste
- reuse of batteries from electric vehicles
- biobased side and waste streams, especially from agriculture and forestry

The consortium consists of 17 partners from seven European countries and it is coordinated by VTT. MTK is in the project in particular to boost circular economy in the sectors of agriculture and forestry.

Links:

Digital marketplace:
www.KiertoaSuomesta.fi

TREASOURcE -project website:
www.treasure.eu

Project information in Finnish:
www.mtk.fi/treasure

KiertoaSuomesta.fi

Marketplace for
biobased side streams

3-page booklet presenting the digital marketplace, English version, 2/2

KiertoaSuomesta.fi -marketplace

KiertoaSuomesta.fi is a digital marketplace that connects sellers and buyers of materials. The site focuses in particular on the trade of bio-based side streams. The service creates new business opportunities for farms and promotes the market for side streams.

The main target groups are companies producing biobased side streams from agriculture, forestry and food processing, as well as industries using raw materials, and the public sector. The service is free of charge.

Log-in page of the marketplace.

Digital marketplace promoting circular bioeconomy

The service contributes to the development of regional nutrient recycling and promotes the circular economy. It also reduces waste and emissions and keeps natural resources in use for longer. The site provides information on the circular economy and its potential.

Examples of side streams

- manure, sludge
- contaminated feed
- grass
- straw
- berry seeds and skins
- logging residues
- bark
- wetland vegetation

This is how it works:

1. Registration:

Register with your email and business ID. Once logged in, you can create sale or purchase listings and view additional information, address and contact details.

2. Creating a post:

From the top of the page, select "Create a post", choose whether you are selling or buying, and specify the category of the product.

3. Details:

Enter as much detail as possible about the material, set a price and attach a picture if possible.

4. Trade and transaction:

The transaction takes place outside the platform via the contact details.

Contact

Nora Berglund
Project Manager
nora.berglund@mtk.fi
+35850 577 3827

Riina Kärki
Project Manager
(parental leave until 8/2025)
riina.karki@mtk.fi

info@kiertoasuomesta.fi

Scan the QR code and register now!

Business card sized flyer for events (in Finnish)

KiertoaSuomesta.fi
Biopohjaisten sivuvirtojen
markkinapaikka

Markkinapaikka biopohjaisille
sivuvirroille (mm. lanta ja olki). Liity
mukaan luomaan uutta liiketoimintaa.
Rekisteröidy nyt ja jätä osto- tai myynti-
ilmoituksesi jo tänään!

www.KiertoaSuomesta.fi info@kiertoasuomesta.fi

Biokaasualan tukien jatkuminen on varmistettava

Biokaasu mahdollistaa biopohjaisten sivuvirtojen ja jätteiden muuttamisen uusiutuvaksi energiaksi sekä kierrätysravinteiksi. **Biokaasun tuotanto lisää yhteiskuntamme huoltovarmuutta energian sekä lannoitteiden suhteen, tukee paikallistalouden suotuisaa kehitystä ja samalla edesauttaa Suomen hiilineutraalisuustavoitteita vähentämällä päästöjä.** Biokaasualan kehitystä Suomessa on vauhdittanut viime vuosina lisääntynyt nesteytetyn biokaasun käyttö raskaan liikenteen polttoaineena. Vuonna 2022 Suomessa tuotettiin 0,9 terawattituntia (TWh) biokaasua. Arvioitu teknistaloudellinen tuotantopotentiaali on kuitenkin 10 TWh, josta jopa 86 % pohjautuu maataloussyötteisiin. Elokuussa 2024 alan toimialajärjestöjen julkaisema Biokaasuvisio asettaa tavoitteeksi tuotannon nostamisen neljään terawattituntiin vuoteen 2030 mennessä. Maatalouden sivuvirtojen (lanta, nurmi, olki) tehokas ja optimoitu hyödyntäminen mahdollistaa biokaasutuotannon, jonka taloudellinen, ekologinen ja sosiaalinen merkitys on suuri yhteiskunnallemme.

Biokaasun tuotanto olisi mahdollista yli kymmenkertaistaa nykyisestä, pääasiassa hyödyntämällä maatalouden sivuvirrat tehokkaammin. Elokuussa 2024 julkaistu biokaasun julkilausuma asettaa tavoitteeksi 4 TWh tuotannon vuodelle 2030.

Kuva: Muokattu versio Biokaasuvisio 2030 -julkilausumasta

Eri puolilla maata on käynnissä useita eri kokoluokan biokaasulaitoshankkeita – sekä suuria teollisen luokan investointeja että pieniä maatilamittakaavan laitoksia. Hankkeita jarruttavat biokaasun tuotantoon liittyvät kannattavuushaasteet sekä sen asema ja tulevaisuus energiasektorilla. Uusiutuvien kaasujen ja kierrätyslannoitteiden markkinat ovat vasta kehitymässä, mikä nostaa investointien riskitasoa. Investointitukien riittämättömyys vähentää investointien määrää ja erilaisille alaa eteenpäin vieville kannustimille on tarve alan elinkelpoisuuden varmistamiseksi. Pienimuotoinen ja alkuvaiheen biopolttoaineiden tuotanto on fossiilisia polttoaineita kalliimpaa, ja markkinoiden kehittämisvaiheessa tarvitaan kannustimia.

Biokaasualan tukimuodot sekä mekanismit tarvitsevat ennakoitavuutta ja poliittisilla päätöksillä on suuri vaikutus alan kehitykseen. Erityisiä haasteita ovat aiheuttaneet biokaasulaitosten tuen väheneminen sekä polttoaineiden jakeluelvoitteen muutokset, kuten velvoitetasojen alentaminen, muutokset jakeluelvoitteen soveltamisalassa (synteettiset polttoaineet, sähkö) ja tulevat muutokset sakkomaksuihin. Maaseutualueilla kaasuverkoston saavutettavuus aiheuttaa alueellista epätasa-arvoa, mikä korostaa logistiikkatuen tarpeen selvittämistä. Vuonna 2020 laadittu kansallinen biokaasuohjelma tulee päivittää ja varmistaa tukien jatkuvuus ja biokaasun aseman vakiinnuttaminen sääntelyssä.

Suosituksia Suomen päättäjille

- 1 Suomen on päivitettävä pääministeri Marinin hallituksen vuonna 2020 julkaisema kansallinen biokaasuohjelma ja varmistettava ohjelman jatkuminen.
- 2 Biokaasulaitosten investointitukien ja ravinteiden kierrätyksen avustuksien jatkuminen on varmistettava.
- 3 Liikennepolttoaineiden jakeluelvoitteen lisävelvoitteen tasoa on nostettava biokaasun kysynnän lisäämiseksi.
- 4 Kaasukäyttöisten raskaan liikenteen ajoneuvojen hankintatukea tulee myöntää myös jatkossa biokaasun kysynnän lisäämiseksi. Tuki tulisi laajentaa myös joukkoliikenteen ja jakeluautojen hankintaan.
- 5 Biokaasun asema raskaan liikenteen ja laivaliikenteen päästösääntelyssä on vakiinnutettava biokaasua suosivaksi.
- 6 Kuljetustuen mahdollisuutta biometaanin kuljettamiseksi maakaasuverkkoon syötettäväksi on selvitettävä.

Esimerkkitapaus

Biokaasuinvestointeihin tarkoitettujen määrärahojen riittämättömyys

Suomessa biokaasuinvestointien rahoitusmahdollisuudet ovat rajalliset. Maatilat ja maatilayhteisöt voivat saada rahoitusta maa- ja metsätalousministeriöltä, mutta budjetti on rajallinen. Esimerkiksi kunnat ja kuntien omistamat yritykset, kuten jätevedenpuhdistamot, voivat tällä hetkellä saada rahoitusta biokaasuinvestointeihinsa ympäristöministeriöltä, jos hankkeessa otetaan huomioon myös ravinteiden kierrätyksen näkökulma. Tämä tuki on kuitenkin päättymässä ja viimeiset hakumahdollisuudet ovat vuonna 2024.

Työ- ja elinkeinoministeriö (TEM) myöntää edelleen tukia myös biokaasuinvestoinneille. TEM:n energiatukien määrärahat ovat kuitenkin pienentyneet viime vuoden 100 miljoonasta eurosta 14 miljoonaan euroon vuonna 2024 (TEM, 2024). Rahoitusvaltuus on Business Finlandilla, ja rahoitusta on päätetty myöntää vain lisäuuutusarvoa tuoviin biokaasulaitosinvestointeihin, muun muassa uutta teknologiaa hyödyntäviin laitoksiin. EU:n ylimääräistä RRF-rahoitusta on ollut haettavissa 2024 asti, mutta rahoitus on nyt päättymässä.

Tämä policy brief on tuotettu osana TREASoURcE-hankkeen työpakettia ”Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains” (Kohdearvoketjujen lainsäädäntö- ja sääntelykehys). Se tarjoaa poliittisille päättäjille ja sidosryhmille perustan kehittää tehokkaita toimintatapoja, joilla edistetään kiertotaloussiirtymää. Tämä policy brief pohjautuu toteutettuun kirjallisuusselvitykseen sekä sidosryhmäyöskentelyyn, jonka avulla validoitiin löydökset. Hankkeen raportissa [D1.3 Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains](#) käsitellään kriittisiä haasteita ja mahdollisuuksia kiertotaloussiirtymän edistämiseksi.

Julkaisu: 10/2024

Kirjoittajat: Nora Berglund, Tran Ngo, Elina Yli-Rantala, Anne-Christine Ritschkoff, Jaana Koivisto, Pirkko Eteläaho, Aila Maijanen, Kaisa Simola

Lisätieto: Nora Berglund, nora.berglund@mtk.fi

Toimittaja: Kaisa Simola

Taitto: Petra Ylikantola

Partnerit

Lähteet

Tilastokeskus. 2023. Energian hankinta ja kulutus, haettu 2.9.2024, www.stat.fi/energia

Martinen, S., Luostarinen, S., Winquist, E., & Timonen, K. 2015. Rural biogas: feasibility and role in Finnish energy system. Cluster for Energy and Environment: Helsinki, Finland.

Biokaasuvisio2030. 2024. Biokaasuvisio2030-julkilausuma, haettu 2.9.2024.

https://biokaasu2030.fi/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/Biokaasuvisio2030_14082024.pdf

TREASoURcE on nelivuotinen (2022–2026) EU:n Horisontti Eurooppa -ohjelman rahoittama hanke, jonka tavoitteena on edistää kiertotaloutta alueellisten kiertotalouspilottien avulla. Projektin keskiössä on kolme arvoketjua: hyödyntämätön muovijäte, sähköautojen akkujen uusiokäyttö sekä biopohjaiset sivuvirrat ja jätteet. Monipuolista sidosryhmätyötä hyödyntäen hankkeen tavoitteena on lisätä merkittävästi tuotteiden ja materiaalien kiertoa sekä kansalaisten kiertotalousosaamista Pohjoismaissa ja Itämeren alueella.

treasource.eu

Euroopan unionin
rahoittama

Euroopan unionin rahoittama. Näkemykset ja mielipiteet ovat kuitenkin kirjoittajien omia, eivätkä välttämättä heijasta Euroopan unionin tai Euroopan tutkimusneuvoston (REA) näkemyksiä. Euroopan unionia tai rahoittajaviranomaista ei voida pitää niistä vastuullisina.

ANNEX 4 – ØSTFOLD – Flowchart for potential utilization of straw

Potential Biogas from Straw

